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Final Handbook with Innovation Factsheets

Insect-borne prokaryote-associated diseases in tropical and subtropical perennial crops

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Introduction

TROPICSAFE addresses three economically important insect-borne prokaryote-associated diseases of perennial crops (palm, citrus and grapevine) grown in tropical and subtropical areas. During the last decades, these are the diseases most seriously affecting the worldwide trade and import of products and materials from these crops, because of the globalization of trade and climate change. The target diseases are due to the presence of diverse '*Candidatus Phytoplasma*' species associated with lethal yellowing in palms and yellows in grapevine, and '*Ca. Liberibacter*' associated with "huanglongbing" in citrus. For their effective, efficient and sustainable (economically and environmentally) management important knowledge gaps were filled working on tropical and subtropical areas in Africa (Ghana, South Africa and Mozambique), America (Mexico, Chile) and the Caribbean (Guadeloupe, Jamaica, Cuba), as well as subtropical regions in Europe (Spain and Italy). TROPICSAFE was based on the concept that knowledge of disease cycles provides strategies for their management and spread prevention. A key challenge in addressing this issue is the interdisciplinary approach, capable of covering all aspects of disease control, and to release a complete model for each selected pathosystem. This ranged from rapid and efficient pathogen/insect vector detection and identification to integrated pest management systems, enclosing environmental, social and economic aspects.

Coconut palms lethal yellowing

Outbreaks of lethal yellowing are threatening the coconut industry economy and the livelihood of millions of rural inhabitants, especially in Central America, the Caribbean and Africa. The disease also has serious environmental repercussions related to soil degradation and negative effects on species biodiversity; moreover, coconut palm cultivation can significantly contribute to carbon sequestration. Several different phytoplasmas are involved in coconut lethal yellowing worldwide, not all of them being well known.

The project surveys in Africa resulted in the identification of '*Candidatus Phytoplasma palmicola*' strains in coconut palms in Ghana and in Mozambique. In Ghana three alternative plant host species and putative insect vectors, respectively were identified. Evaluation of five dwarf coconut varieties showed that two of them are having a superior growth in heavily infected areas. In Cuba, Jamaica and Mexico the 16SrIV phytoplasma group was detected in coconut species, and *Haplaxius crudus* was confirmed as insect vector in Mexico. In Jamaica *Stachytarpheta jamaicensis* and *Cleome rutidosperma* were positive for group 16SrIV phytoplasmas, while *H. crudus* and *Oecleus mackaspringii* are possible insect vectors. In Mexico alternative plant host species were identified of which some are hosting nymphs of *H. crudus*; several putative alternative insect vectors were also identified. Different palm ecotypes are under field evaluation for resistance also using specifically

developed molecular markers. Resistant germplasm from Mexico has been transferred as *in vitro* plants to Cuba and Jamaica to compare its performance in diverse geographic areas. A new LAMP diagnostic system for detecting the phytoplasma was applied. A PCR multiplex methodology, based on the *secA* gene, to distinguish between 16SrIV-A and 16SrIV-D phytoplasmas was developed.

🌀 Grapevine yellows disease

Grapevine yellows in tropical and subtropical areas resulted mainly associated with '*Ca. P. asteris*' in South Africa, '*Ca. P. fraxini*' and '*Ca. P. pruni*' in Chile, '*Ca. P. solani*' in the Mediterranean basin all of them causing serious economic losses. In South Africa the '*Ca. P. asteris*' was detected in *Mesembryanthemum crystallinum*, *Protea cynaroides*, and *Raphanus sativus*; it was also identified in the insects *Aconurella prolixa* and *Exitianus* sp. The most abundant insect species in vineyards was *Mgenia fuscovaria*, reported as vector of the phytoplasma that showed several peaks in the year. A management plan has been developed including recommendations for leafhopper monitoring, weed control, sanitation and chemical control. Potential biological control agents of leafhoppers were also identified. Plant-derived antimicrobial peptides were prepared and preliminary screenings against phytoplasma-containing colonies were performed. The developed LAMP and qPCR assays for specific detection of the '*Ca. P. asteris*' South African strain were tested on synthetic target DNA, on DNA samples from different 16S phytoplasma ribosomal groups, and on grapevine samples from South Africa. Both assays exhibited suitable performance characteristics.

In Chile alternative host plants for the '*Ca. P. pruni*' (16SrIII-J) were *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Galega officinalis*, *Polygonum aviculare*, *Brassica rapa*, *Malva* sp., *Erodium cicutarium*, *Rosa* sp. and *Rubus ulmifolius*. *Amplicephalus curtulus*, *A. ornatus*, *A. pallidus*, *Exitianus obscurinervis*, *Bergallia* sp., and *Paratanus exitiosus* were identified as insect vectors or potential vectors of this phytoplasma, the dominant species being *P. exitiosus*, followed by *A. curtulus*. In Italy plants and insect samples collected in vineyards and positive for the presence of diverse grapevine phytoplasmas belonged to 16 and 12 species, respectively. The main phytoplasma diseases target for management and detection were "bois noir" and "flavescence dorée". An experimental vineyard obtained with the F1 crossing population between genotypes with differential susceptibility to "flavescence dorée" was infected using insect vectors. Genotyping the individuals of the F1 population was carried out on 300 biotypes and the results showed that

approximately 20% of the progeny was self-crossed. A total of 188 samples were selected and GBS sequenced to identify genes putatively associated to the susceptibility/resistance of varieties with opposite phenotypes. To assess the analytical performances of the developed serological detection protocol for phytoplasmas on sample sources other than grapevine, a comparative analysis of the ELISA *versus* qPCR was carried out. Sample storage experiments allowed verification of the storage conditions of grapevine tissue for up to 5 months for freeze-dried samples. Antisera produced using phytoplasma colonies of '*Ca. P. asteris*' were tested by the immunofluorescence assay (IFAS) and were able to detect the agent in cell cultures and periwinkle phytoplasma infected samples.

Citrus “huanglongbing” disease

“Huanglongbing” is the most destructive disease of commercial citrus species worldwide. Its impact is very high in America and Africa and one of his insect vectors occurs in the Iberian Peninsula, the main citrus producing area of Europe. The ‘*Ca. Liberibacter*’ species infects all citrus varieties and information concerning alternative plant and insect hosts is missing. Surveys in citrus orchards confirmed the presence of ‘*Ca. L. africanus*’ in South Africa and ‘*Ca. L. asiaticus*’ in Guadeloupe, Jamaica, Mexico and Cuba, but none of these bacteria was detected in the surveys carried out in five citrus-growing regions of Chile and in Spain. Surveys did not result in the detection of alternative insect or plant host species. The presence of the known vectors *Diaphorina citri* in Cuba, Mexico and Guadeloupe, and *Trioza erytreae* in South Africa was confirmed. Since native parasitoids of *T. erytreae* were not identified in Spain, *Tamarixia dryi* from South Africa was introduced and showed good dispersion and parasitism efficacy in the Canary Islands first, and in Spain later. The seasonal trend of *T. erytreae* determined in the Canary Islands indicated between four and five generations per year, but its population remained very low after the summer. Several predictive models developed to estimate the invasion risk of *T. erytreae* in the citrus growing areas of Europe, Near East and North Africa demonstrates that the psyllid would probably establish in all the citrus growing regions of this geographic areas.

A survey for the disease presence in the main citrus producing areas of Cuba confirmed its presence throughout the island. The seasonal trend of *D. citri* was connected to management strategies, and irrigation or rains. Elimination of the symptomatic trees at a regional scale resulted in the best management strategy. The efficacy of kaolin against *D. citri* resulted keeping the infestation level very low for two years. In Guadeloupe, despite the relatively low abundance of *D. citri* in some orchards under an integrated pest management program, the disease levels and mortality of the citrus trees were very high. Different combinations of rootstocks/varieties were selected and, after four years from plantation, all the trees became infected although they were asymptomatic and had fruits. The quantitative PCR analysis revealed the presence of a low concentration of ‘*Ca. L. asiaticus*’; the relationship between “huanglongbing” susceptibility and anatomical, physiological, and metabolomic traits with a special focus on the potential impact of polyploidy on tolerance to the disease, was determined. A specific real-time LAMP was established for the detection of ‘*Ca. L. africanus*’ in South Africa.

COCONUT

LETHAL YELLOWING

■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

The importance of coconut in the TROPICSAFE partner countries

One of the aims of TROPICSAFE is to evaluate the impact of the solutions proposed to manage lethal yellowing, one of the most serious diseases affecting coconut in the world. The focus is made on Jamaica, Ghana, and Mexico, where the spread of the disease in the last decades has been responsible for the loss of an overwhelming majority of coconut production. The analysis is carried out using mainly official data from FAOSTAT, integrated with information available on academic literature, as well as data published by agribusiness organizations.

Economic and social aspects are considered to define the relative importance of the crop at national and international level and, in particular, the consequences of the disease on the local agri-food chain and the exchange with other countries. The dynamics of production, yields, and import-export also give an idea about the entity of the loss and the capacities of the national system to face the crisis.

- Coconut palm ovary used for the pollination by hand to obtain productive hybrids.

■ LATEST RESEARCH RESULTS

Overview on the importance of worldwide coconut production

Coconut is the sixth most cultivated fruit in the world: it is grown in 87 countries, covers 11.8 million hectares, has an annual production of almost 63 million tonnes of nuts (FAOSTAT, 2019), and provides a gross production value of USD\$ 9.7 billions (FAOSTAT, 2018). Around 73% of the world area producing coconut is concentrated in the Philippines (31%), Indonesia (24%), and India (18%). Jamaica and Ghana occupy a marginal position of worldwide coconut production (0.2% and 0.6% respectively), while Mexico is one of the ten biggest producers. The coconut trade is mainly in processed products (coconuts desiccated, copra, coconut oil). Indonesia is the leader export country followed by Thailand and Vietnam. On the import side, China is the first importer followed by the United

States of America and the Netherlands (FAOSTAT 2019). The figure below shows the spreading of lethal yellowing disease in the main producing countries. In Ghana, the Cape Saint Paul wilt disease (CSPWD) caused the collapse of the coconut industry in the 1950s (Leather, 1959). The disease has been responsible for the death of over 7 million palms in Jamaica in the 1980s, and the country is recurrently devastated by epidemic outbreaks (Lebrun *et al.*, 2008). In Mexico over the last two decades of the 20th Century, the lethal yellowing epidemic disease led to a drop of 60,000 ha in cultivated area, and a decrease in cultivation density from 100 trees per hectare to just 60 (Zizumbo-Villarreal *et al.*, 2006).

- World map of annual coconut production and published occurrences of lethal yellowing-type diseases of palms production (Gurr *et al.*, 2016).

■ THE TROPICSAFE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

The coconut market in Jamaica, Ghana, and Mexico

Jamaica: According to the Coconut Industry Board (CIB), a public body promoting the efficiency and the interests of the coconut businesses, the production is provided basically by small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The majority of farms have a surface smaller than 10 ha. In 2019 coconut crops covered around 15,796 ha with a production of 99,200 tons (FAOSTAT, 2019). Since the lethal yellowing destroyed both local and hybrids varieties, several management strategies have been implemented to reduce the spread of the disease. The CIB has also promoted the distribution to farmers of seedlings of the resistant variety Special Malayan Dwarf Yellows.

Ghana: In this country, coconut is the most important cash crop along the coastal belt mainly due to its various by-products. Data available in academic literature reported that, since the first incidence of the disease in 1932, the three main regions of coconut production (the Western, Central, and Volta Regions) have been devastated (Danyo, 2011). More recently, both coconut production and export have increased significantly. According to FAO data, in 2019, the coconut production amounts to 403,905 tons on 75,195 ha. Around 80% of the coconuts are produced by smallholder farmers. The export of desiccated coconuts totaled USD\$1.4 million – but currently, most coconuts are consumed locally.

Mexico: Mexico ranked 7th in the worldwide coconut production in 2019, accounting for 1,287,957 tons cultivated on about 204,133 ha. Mexican dry climate, as well as the distance among plantations, resulted in lethal yellowing outbreaks less explosive than in other countries, such as Jamaica, with higher rainfall and higher density of palm plantations (Mora-Aguillera, 2002).

- Coconut production (tons) in Jamaica, Ghana, and Mexico 1961-2018 (tons) (FAOSTAT).

■ SCIENTIFIC DATA AND FIRST RESULTS

Socioeconomic consideration on the lethal yellowing on coconut agri-food chain

Coconut is a very important commercial crop in many tropical and subtropical countries, including Jamaica, Ghana, and Mexico, contributing significantly to their economies. Coconut flesh, indeed, can be used in the food, cosmetic and energy industries. The importance of coconut in each production country lies in several issues ranging from social, economic to environmental concerns. Coconut palms play a crucial role in local cultures, and coconuts provide livelihood security to millions of worldwide smallholders. From a more economic standpoint, coconut acquires substantial significance for rural employment and income generation. A crucial characteristic of coconut, indeed, is its capacity to create employment in marginal rural areas, where there are a few other opportunities. In this sense, and in determined local contexts, the socioeconomic cost of lethal yellowing is dramatic, considering the impact not only on the production, but also on employments loss. Finally, coconut plantations require low to no inputs and can provide wildlife and habitat conservation, contributing to carbon sequestration and preventing coastal erosion. In these circumstances, a systematic and timely pathogen detection becomes highly important for effective control and management of the disease. In the countries involved in TROPICSAFE, several management strategies are currently being implemented. In Ghana, the government has recently launched the Planting for Export and Rural Development (PERD) initiative by providing smallholders with hybrid coconut seeds, leading to improved yield. Jamaica is promoting many activities to reduce the spread of lethal yellowing and it is currently experimenting the cultivation of hybrids resistant to the disease. In Mexico, since 2016, lethal yellowing-resistant seedlings have been added to the coconut stock as recovery program of the Ministry of Agriculture.

The coconut tree bears the coconut fruit, which is used for nutrition, fuel, and shelter. Its cultivation is also one of the most sustainable practices on Earth.

- Various uses of coconut.

KEY WORDS

Coconut, market, socio-economic aspects, lethal yellowing disease

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

The importance of slowing down the death of coconut palms from infection by phytoplasmas

Phytoplasmas of coconut in Africa are associated with lethal-yellowing type diseases, and have been responsible for the death of many palms in coastal regions of west and east Africa. These diseases are also responsible for destroying the livelihoods of many small-scale subsistence farmers and for the collapse of the coconut industry in countries such as Ghana and Mozambique. The original epidemic in Ghana caused the collapse of the coconut industry in the Volta region by the 1950s, and the more recent epidemic in the Central and Western regions has killed well over one million coconut palms to date (Eziashi and Omamor, 2010). These phytoplasmas have been classified into the 16SrXXII-A '*Candidatus Phytoplasma palmicola*' in the Cameroon, Nigeria and Mozambique, 16SrXXII-B '*Ca. P. palmicola*'-related strains in Ghana and Cote d'Ivoire, and the Tanzanian lethal disease in Tanzania and Kenya. These latter phytoplasmas are different from those associated with the lethal yellowing disease of coconut in Mexico and the Caribbean, which all belong to the 16SrIV groups (Harrison et al., 2014).

Promising resistant hybrid palm genotypes have been screened in Ghana to the 16SrXXII-B phytoplasmas, and the only current efficient management options for the disease are the rapid and systematic removal and burning of infected palms, to remove the reservoir of phytoplasmas, followed by replanting with healthy palms. One factor that can significantly improve the success of such a strategy is the rapid detection of infections in palms, so that they can be removed before they have had the chance to spread the disease to the neighbouring palms. This factsheet details the development and deployment of a rapid 20 minutes in-field system for the 16SrXXII '*Ca. P. palmicola*' detection in coconut in Africa.

- Dead coconut palms resulting from infection with the 16SrXXII-B '*Candidatus Phytoplasma palmicola*' in Ghana (Fabian Pilet, CIRAD).

■ LATEST RESEARCH RESULTS

Rapid diagnostic method to reduce the spreading of coconut phytoplasmas

Diagnostic methods for coconut phytoplasma detection worldwide generally require samples of trunk borings collected from palms in the field to be transported to the laboratory for DNA extraction, then testing by conventional polymerase chain reaction (PCR) with the results analysed through gel electrophoresis. Because of the remoteness of diseased areas in many countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, this can often take two or more days from sampling to final results. In-field loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) detection systems have been shown to be much quicker than PCR with the advantage that they can work on relatively impure DNA samples. Portable, battery operated LAMP machines that can be deployed in the field in remote locations have been developed, which display the detection of LAMP reaction products within 15-20 minutes. In addition, LAMP reagent master mixes have been developed that are stable at ambient temperatures for at least a month, so can be transported to these remote locations.

- Collecting trunk borings from coconut palms for DNA extraction in the field in Ghana.

■ THE TROPICSAFE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

The TROPICSAFE contribution to improve the in-field LAMP detection systems

The aim of the work within TROPICSAFE was to design and validate primers that are specific for the coconut phytoplasmas. These can then be incorporated with the master mixes and detection systems for in-field LAMP detection of the coconut diseases, and also to develop and validate a rapid DNA extraction system from trunk borings that can be undertaken with minimal equipment. The overall goal is to develop and validate a detection system that can detect the presence of the specific phytoplasmas in coconut palms within 20 minutes from start to finish in remote locations using a minimal equipment.

LAMP primers have been designed based on the sequence of the '*Ca. P. palmicola*' *leuS* gene that are able to detect the 16SrXXII-A and 16SrXXII-B phytoplasmas within 15-20 minutes in the LAMP diagnostic assay system. These primers have been validated against samples from Ghana, Nigeria and Mozambique, and have also been shown to have no cross reaction to the phytoplasmas from coconut in Tanzania, DNA from 16SrIV-A (coconut lethal yellows) phytoplasmas from the USA and Mexico, 16SrIV-D phytoplasmas from coconut in Mexico, or phytoplasmas from other ribosomal groups (16SrI, 16SrII, 16SrIII, 16SrV, 16SrVI, 16SrIX, 16SrX, 16SrXI and 16SrXIV). In addition, a DNA extraction procedure has been validated based on the alkaline PEG method of Chomczynski and Rymaszewski (2006), in which 10-20 mg of coconut trunk borings is placed directly from the drill tip into 500 µl alkaline PEG buffer and it is grounded for 30 seconds with a disposable plastic micropestle. One microlitre of the supernatant is then used directly in the LAMP reaction. To confirm that the quality of the extracted DNA is suitable for LAMP, a second set of primers has also been designed that detect the coconut cytochrome oxidase gene.

- Setting up LAMP diagnostics with a portable equipment for DNA extraction and phytoplasma detection in the field.

■ SCIENTIFIC DATA AND FIRST RESULTS

Tests in the field in Ghana and potential for the testing in Caribbean and America

A LAMP diagnostic assay has been developed for the use in the field for rapid and specific detection of the 16SrXXII coconut lethal yellowing phytoplasmas in Africa. This assay has been combined with a rapid DNA extraction system that uses minimal equipment such that trunk boring samples can be tested from individual palms in the field and results confirmed within 20-30 minutes from the extraction. In effect, each trunk boring sample is tested with two sets of primers simultaneously in the portable LAMP machine, one set for the 16SrXXII phytoplasma DNA, and the second set for the coconut DNA. Any sample that tests positive with the phytoplasma primers can be deemed positive for the presence of the phytoplasma, whilst any sample that tests negative with the phytoplasma primers, but positive with the coconut primers can be deemed to be negative for the presence of detectable levels of these phytoplasmas and therefore most likely uninfected. Any sample that tests negative with both sets of primers is deemed to contain inhibitors of the LAMP reaction enzymes (or not containing DNA) and would need to be retested from a new DNA extraction. The method has been tested in the field in Ghana and with stored trunk boring samples sent to the University of Nottingham, UK. In addition, a separate set of primers have been developed for specific detection of the 16SrIV-A and the 16SrIV-D phytoplasmas of coconut, which have the potential for rapid in-field detection in the coconut palms in the Caribbean and the Americas, where these phytoplasmas are the ones associated with the coconut lethal yellowing.

- A LAMP detection profile for the 16SrXXII phytoplasmas. Wells 1 and 2 show positive reactions from phytoplasma infected palms whilst wells 3-7 show negative reactions and well 8 is a water control.

KEY WORDS

LAMP, lethal yellowing diseases, in-field detection, phytoplasmas

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DETECTION OF TWO STRAINS OF THE COCONUT LETHAL YELLOWING PHYTOPLASMA IN A SINGLE TEST

Lethal yellowing phytoplasmas detected using a quantitative PCR assay

■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Detection of the two predominant strains of lethal yellowing phytoplasmas in Mexico

Coconut is a palm species cultivated worldwide. It is very important because several products can be obtained from it, particularly from the fruit. The markets of coconut products (pack water, virgin oil, and others) are currently growing very fast. Unfortunately, fruit production is slowing down, mainly because phytosanitary issues and old age of plantations. The main phytosanitary problem is lethal yellowing, a devastating disease associated with the presence of phytoplasmas. In America it affects several palm species besides coconut, including *Adonidia merrillii*, *Pritchardia pacifica*, *Phoenix canariensis*. In Mexico, there are two predominant strains of lethal yellowing-associated phytoplasmas, belonging to subgroups 16SrIV-A and 16SrIV-D. They are widely distributed throughout the country and infecting different palm species. Usually, to determine the presence of different lethal yellowing strains, DNA samples from plants or insects are subjected to two rounds of PCR amplification (nested-PCR) and sequencing of the 16S rRNA gene products. But this process is time consuming and expensive.

- Lethal yellowing symptoms in Manila palms (*Adonidia merrillii*) in Yucatán, Mexico. Browning of leaves (A). Necrotic inflorescences (B). A palm with necrosis of spear leaf (C) and close-up of necrotic spear leaf (D). Palm with most of the crown affected (E). Uninfected asymptomatic palm (F) and corresponding inflorescences (G). Manila palms can be infected with phytoplasma strains 16SrIV-A and 16SrIV-D.

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Improved detection of two strains of lethal yellowing phytoplasmas

A new quantitative PCR (qPCR) assay was developed for easier detection and identification of the two strains of lethal yellowing phytoplasma 16SrIV-A and -D. The procedure is based on genetic differences between them reducing the processing time. It increases resource efficiency by eliminating the steps required for running the nested-PCR products, their digestion with restriction enzymes and the determination of the digestion profiles, or sequencing the amplicons.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Development of a new qPCR assay for detection of subgroup 16SrIV-A and -D phytoplasmas in a single tube

With the objective of detecting the two strains of lethal yellowing phytoplasmas predominant in Mexico (16SrIV-A and -D) in a simpler and faster way, the new assay protocol was designed to be carried out in the same tube with a single qPCR reaction.

Specificity and sensitivity of the new assay were evaluated. It was able to detect strains 16SrIV-A and -D, but no other phytoplasmas, and it is capable to detect up to 0.01 ng of phytoplasma DNA. So, the assay represents an improvement in specificity and sensitivity or both in relation to previously reported assays (Bahder *et al.*, 2017; Cordova *et al.*, 2014; Harrison *et al.*, 1999).

Phytoplasma strain (ribosomal subgroup)		qPCR assay		nested-PCR	
Phytoplasmas in palms		16SrIV-A	16SrIV-D		
	Coconut lethal decline, Tanzania ^A	16SrIV-C	-	-	+
	Coconut lethal yellowing, Mozambique ^A	16SrXXII-A	-	-	+
	Coconut lethal yellowing, Florida ^A	16SrIV-A	+	-	+
	Coconut, lethal yellowing, Mexico ^B	16SrIV-A	+	-	+
	<i>Prichardia pacifica</i> , lethal yellowing, Mexico ^B	16SrIV-D	-	+	+
	<i>Adonia merrillii</i> , lethal yellowing, Mexico ^B	16SrIV-D	-	+	+
	Coconut healthy, Mexico ^B	-	-	-	-
	Coconut healthy, Mozambique ^A	-	-	-	-
Other phytoplasmas	' <i>Ca. P. pruni</i> ', strain PWX ^A	16SrIII-A	-	-	+
	' <i>Ca. P. ulmi</i> ', strain EY ^A	16SrV-A	-	-	+
	' <i>Ca. P. ziziphi</i> ', strain JWB ^A	16SrV-B	-	-	+
	' <i>Ca. P. trifolii</i> ', strain BLTVA ^A	16SrVI-A	-	-	+
	' <i>Ca. P. fraxini</i> ', strain ASHY ^A	16SrVII-A	-	-	+
	' <i>Ca. P. hispanicum</i> ', strain MPV ^A	16SrXIII-A	-	-	+
	Strawberry green petals, strain SGP ^A	16SrXIII-B	-	-	+
' <i>Ca. P. cynodontis</i> ', strain BGWL ^A	16SrXIV-A	-	-	+	

Tested in duplicate. (-) not detected; (+) phytoplasma detected; '*Ca. P.*' *Candidatus* Phytoplasma'. Sources of phytoplasma DNA: (A) Dr. Nigel Harrison, University of Florida, FL 33314, USA; and (B) CICY, Mérida, Yucatán, 97205 México.

- Specific detection of phytoplasmas of different ribosomal groups and subgroups with the new qPCR assay versus nested-PCR assay.

qPCR assay detection limit

DNA (ng)	100	10	1	0.1	0.01
16SrIV-A	20.3 ± 0.1	23.5 ± 0.1	27.0 ± 0.1	30.0 ± 0.1	34.0 ± 0.0
16SrIV-D	22.2 ± 0.0	24.8 ± 0.3	28.1 ± 0.1	31.2 ± 0.1	35.0 ± 0.1

- Evaluation of sensitivity of the new qPCR assay protocol for the detection of the phytoplasmas of subgroups 16SrIV-A and 16SrIV-D. The DNA samples used were from an infected coconut palm for 16SrIV-A and from an infected *Adonia merrillii* palm for 16SrIV-D tested in a single tube assay.

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Testing the qPCR assay for the detection of subgroup 16SrIV-A and -D phytoplasmas in a single tube

In order to evaluate how the new qPCR assay is working, a set of samples of DNA obtained from trunk tissue, collected from different palm species displaying symptoms of lethal yellowing, were analyzed and resulted positive for 16SrIV-A or 16SrIV-D phytoplasmas. These results coincided with the sequencing analysis carried out separately. Therefore, they are supporting the capacity of the assay to detect specifically DNA of 16SrIV-A or 16SrIV-D phytoplasmas within a single tube and with a single qPCR reaction. This assay is useful for research and epidemiological purposes.

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Palm species	Symptoms	Non-specific qPCR (Ct)	New qPCR assay specific detection (Ct)		Subgroup according to qPCR assay
			16SrIV-A	16SrIV-D	
Coconut	No	ND	ND	ND	-
Coconut	Yes	16.6	16.5	ND	16SrIV-A*
Coconut	Yes	23.3	22.9	ND	16SrIV-A*
Coconut	Yes	18.24	30.9	ND	16SrIV-A*
<i>Thrinax radiata</i>	Yes	14.58	25.6	ND	16SrIV-A*
<i>Phoenix canariensis</i>	Yes	21.5	ND	28.2	16SrIV-D*
<i>Phoenix canariensis</i>	Yes	23.2	ND	35.1	16SrIV-D*
<i>Phoenix canariensis</i>	Yes	25.7	ND	21.7	16SrIV-D*
<i>Phoenix canariensis</i>	Yes	22.2	ND	19.2	16SrIV-D*

Ct: cycle threshold; ND: No amplification detected. Samples were considered negative if the Ct value was ≥ 37 . Non-specific qPCR assay as reported by Cordova *et al*, 2014. (*) Subgroup confirmed by sequence analysis.

- Detection of phytoplasma strains 16SrIV-A and 16SrIV-D in palm trunk DNA samples using the new qPCR assay. The DNA samples were obtained from palms in Yucatán state (coconut and *Thrinax radiata*) and Coahuila state (*Phoenix canariensis*) in Mexico.

KEY WORDS

Lethal yellowing, phytoplasmas, palms, quantitative PCR

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Lethal yellowing: a great threat to the coconut value chain in many countries

Lethal yellowing is a disease that has killed millions of coconut palms in several countries in the Americas affecting coconut farmers and industry, and its spread is threatening several other countries (Myrie *et al.*, 2019). Effective management of this disease requires resistant germplasm. Fortunately in Jamaica and Mexico, the identification of some resistant genotypes was obtained (Yankey *et al.*, 2018). However further screening is needed of both introduced and local materials to avoid the risk linked to the use of homogeneous germplasm. The screening has to be done in the field exposing palms to insect vectors, a process that takes very long. Replacing susceptible coconut palms with resistant ones is the only long-time sustainable strategy for the coconut industries in several countries.

- Countries where lethal yellowing has been reported in America and the Caribbean (highlighted in yellow).

- Symptoms of lethal yellowing: nut drop (A), inflorescence necrosis (B), leaf yellowing (C) and loss of foliage leaving the bare trunk (CICY).

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE.

Lethal yellowing resistance screening and germplasm transfer to other countries

To develop advanced Integrated Pest Management and new management strategies for lethal yellowing the use of resistant germplasm and therefore the resistance screening are basic activities carried out in the project. The transfer of lethal yellowing-resistant coconut plantlets to other participating countries is also part of the project to help reducing environmental disease impact. This practice is helping to reduce the use of chemicals for insect vector control to prevent the pathogen spreading, and also generates knowledge about germplasm susceptibility under different environments. The lethal yellowing-resistance screening and germplasm exchange activities can also be the basis for the implementation of a permanent system for screening, production and exchange of lethal yellowing-resistant germplasm for coconut-producing countries in selected geographic areas.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Establishment of trials and shipment of plantlets

Screening of lethal yellowing-resistance is implemented by field testing coconut materials of interest in Mexico, these are the varieties Brazilian Green Dwarf, Yucatan Green Dwarf, and Alto Saladita, the first one was introduced to Mexico recently and the other two are local ecotypes. Two trials are monitored in Ojoshal, Tabasco established before the project started, and in Ticul, Yucatan. They consists of two sections one established before the project started and another established as part of the project. The coconuts planted are exposed to insect vectors that are in the environment and in both sites some coconut and other palm species died. These and insects resulted positive to lethal yellowing phytoplasmas by PCR assays (Córdova *et al.*, 2014). Finally, lethal yellowing-resistant germplasm produced *in vitro* is provided in small quantity to Jamaica and Cuba partners to establish trials to test them locally.

- Trials to test the susceptibility of different coconut varieties to lethal yellowing in: (A) Ojoshal, Tabasco; and (B) Chum Copte I and (C) Chum Copte II in Ticul, Yucatán Mexico, (CICY).

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Lethal yellowing screening and germplasm exchange

In the periphery of the Ojoshal trial in Tabasco, phytoplasma presence in weed species and in *Haplaxius crudus* adults and nymphs was confirmed, but no losses of coconut plants within the trial have occurred. In Ticul in Chum Copte I site there have been three losses of coconut palms (0.5%) in which the lethal yellowing phytoplasma was detected; no losses in Chum Copte II site were observed. Hybrid germplasm shipment to other countries with both parents resistant to lethal yellowing in Mexico as reported by Zizumbo *et al.* (2008) was carried out with materials produced by micropropagation in CICY. A batch of 60 plantlets was sent to Coconut Industry Board (CIB) in Jamaica. A batch of 200 plantlets was sent to "Instituto de Fruticultura Tropical" (IIFT), the batch was carried to Cuba also training the personal there for the acclimatization of the plantlets. The screening of coconut germplasm for lethal yellowing-resistance is very advantageous since it allows to have the most effective component for Integrated Pest Management application. Also it is important that screening continues by testing new genotypes to increase diversity, which is relevant for plants to deal with pathogens and for differentiation of products since some coconut varieties are more useful for water production and other for oil production or other purposes. Moreover, the germplasm exchange allows its testing under the recipient country conditions and generate more knowledge about the genotype performances.

- Coconut palms of Yucatan Green Dwarf variety that developed symptoms, were PCR positive to lethal yellowing and died within 2018 in Chum Copte I in Yucatan, Mexico.

- Plantlets of lethal yellowing-resistant coconut produced *in vitro* at CICY in Mexico for shipment (A) and after arrival at destination at CIB in Jamaica (B) and IIFT in Cuba (C).

KEY WORDS

Coconut, lethal yellowing, resistance, disease management

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Lethal yellowing disease: a threat to the coconut industry in Ghana

Coconut is a small-holder crop grown mainly by resource for poor farmers living along the coastal regions of Ghana. It is estimated to support the livelihood of about 8% of the country's rural population. In the Western Region, it is estimated that about 20% of the rural population depend on coconut for sustenance. Coconut tree is referred to worldwide as the "tree of life" and it is the main source of livelihood for several rural communities, providing food, fuel-wood, drink, edible oil, fiber, animal feed and building material with a minimum capital outlay. The crop has great potential for job creation, contributing to food security and increased foreign exchange for Ghana. This potential is, however, challenged by a devastating lethal yellowing disease known locally as Cape St. Paul wilt disease.

• A healthy coconut farm (left) and a lethal yellowing disease devastated farm (right). Photo by J. Nkansah-Poku (left); Egya N. Yankey (right).

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Assessment of the agronomic potential of promising disease resistant coconut varieties

Disease resistance is not a once-forever phenomenon. Large scale deployment of the "Maypan" hybrid in Jamaica suffered massive destruction when the supposed resistance collapsed during the 80's (Broschat *et al.*, 2002). The search for resistant varieties must be a continuous process. In 2007, in collaboration with CIRAD and under the Farmer Support Project sponsored by the French Government, eight dwarf varieties were planted at three disease *foci* in the Central and Western Regions of Ghana to assess their resistance to the disease. Two of the trial sites have been affected by the disease. At both sites, two varieties, IBD and NLD were not showing disease symptoms. Two other varieties, NGBD and MGD have recorded low disease incidence levels of 1.21% and 1.19% respectively. The agronomic performance of these varieties, however, needs still to be determined so that both disease resistant and high yielding materials can be released to farmers.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Field assessment of the productivity of promising coconut varieties

Under the framework of TROPICSAFE, the agronomic performance of the above-mentioned varieties that have shown promising/potential resistance to Cape Saint Paul wilt disease was evaluated. The trials are carried out at Anwea, a disease endemic area in the Western Region where coconut was the major cultivated tree crop before being replaced by cocoa because of the phytoplasma epidemic disease. The district is characterized by all year round rainfall and good textured soils which support the cultivation of different types of crops. The trial has been set up using a randomized complete block design. The SGD, SGD x VTT hybrid and the West African Tall type (susceptible control) have been included. Varietal vigour is assessed by collecting growth parameters such leaf emission, number of leaflets, plant girth, petiole length and total leaf length on 30 palms of each variety at six-monthly intervals. The palms are also observed for symptoms of Cape Saint Paul wilt disease.

• The trial field at Anwea.

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Data collection and monitoring of palms

After two years of planting, none of the palms have shown disease symptoms. The palms are expected to start producing flowers and fruits in 2021. At this time, yield and other reproductive data will be collected and used to ascertain yield stability, uniformity, and distinctiveness of the different coconut varieties. A long time is required to collect such data from coconut plantations. However, it is expected that the initial data, along with the growth data, will indicate the value of each coconut variety being assessed. The outcome of the trial will give hope to the Ghanaian coconut farmers and facilitate the revival of the replanting program in Ghana.

• Measurement of collar girth (left) and fertilization to maximise the potential of the palms (right).

KEY WORDS

Coconut, agronomic performance, resistance, lethal yellowing, disease

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EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR COCONUT LETHAL YELLOWING DISEASE IN JAMAICA

Impact on of management practices on the spread of the disease

■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Sustainable lethal yellowing management for the coconut industry in Jamaica

Lethal yellowing is a devastating disease that affects coconut as well as 35 other palm species. It most commonly occurs in the Caribbean, Latin America and Africa and since 1961 has killed millions of palms. The relentless spread of this fatal disease throughout the coconut growing areas is having a serious impact on many vulnerable communities. Phytoplasmas enclosed in the 16SrIV group are associated with the disease. These phytopathogenic bacteria systemically colonize the phloem tissues inducing numerous biochemical and physiological changes leading to symptom development and ultimate death of coconut palms.

- Geographic locations of areas affected by lethal yellowing disease in Jamaica (left) and symptomatic coconut tree (right).

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Management strategies needed for the control of lethal yellowing disease spread

One of the main aims of the TROPICSAFE project is to develop advanced pest integrated management strategies through the reduction of the environmental impact of plant protection strategies. Among these strategies, the use of cultural practices and spot chemical application in the overall management strategies to control the spread of the disease resulted to some extent effective. The project aims to evaluate the effect of these management strategies in the disease containment.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Validation of the management practices to reduce the spread of lethal yellowing disease

The disease was reduced significantly in some of the most affected areas in Jamaica. These areas were identified, and the management practices were applied systematically following the below protocol:

1. Surveillance of the lethal yellowing infected areas
2. Identification of the trees that are affected
3. Test the trees for lethal yellowing phytoplasma presence
4. Immediate removal of the infected/symptomatic trees
5. Spot spraying of insecticide (malathion) to control insect vectors or potential vectors such as *Haplaxius crudus* and *Oecleus* sp.
6. Immediate replanting of healthy coconut seedlings near the area where the infected trees are removed
7. Undertake weed control by elimination of cynodon grass, Saint Augustine grass, Guinea grass, *Emilia fosbergii* and *Stachytarpheta jamaicensis*
8. Manage plant health through the application of appropriate fertilization.

• Removal of lethal yellowing infected tree and collection of insects from the leaves of the removed trees.

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Encouraging results

The analysis of the data collected shows a reduction in the number of trees becoming infected in the area where the management strategies are being implemented. The spread of the disease in these areas continues to trend downwards and give renewed hope to small holders in the rural coconut communities in Jamaica. The graph shows the effect of the management practice, where the disease was reduced significantly over time.

• Numbers of coconut palm deaths due to lethal yellowing disease since 2002 at the Nutts River farm in Jamaica.

KEY WORDS

Management strategies, lethal yellowing, disease, phytoplasmas

MORE INFORMATION

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

The history of coconut lethal yellowing in Cuba

Among the more serious phytoplasma diseases are lethal yellowing of palms (Eziashi and Omamor, 2010). In Cuba, coconut is used as ornamental plant and some small commercial plantations are present in Baracoa (Guantánamo province), Niquero y Pílon (Granma province) and some municipalities from the central region (Cueto, 1986). In previous report the Cuban lethal yellowing associated phytoplasmas were classified in the 16SrIV group (Llauger *et al.*, 2002). Nowadays there is a National Program to recover the Cuban coconut industry and in this frame it was very relevant to verify the identity of phytoplasmas associated with lethal yellowing to support the further development of strategies to more effectively monitor and manage the disease in the country.

- Symptomatology observed in the coconut trees: yellow leaves in horizontal position and necrotic inflorescences.

■ LATEST RESEARCH RESULTS

The phytoplasma detected in coconut

Coconut lethal yellowing is the most important disease presently affecting the coconut production worldwide. Symptomatic and asymptomatic coconut plants were sampled in some selected areas to verify the identity of phytoplasmas present in Cuba. Diverse phytoplasma ribosomal groups were detected in the samples from symptomatic palms such as 16SrXII, 16SrVII, and 16SrI. In several other palms 16SrIV-A subgroup phytoplasmas were identified. In the *groEL* gene the only positive plant from Pílon resulted infected with a phytoplasma that is diverse from the others and identical to the 16SrIV-A strains detected in Jamaica infected coconut palms. The project survey allows the first record of occurrence of 16SrI, -VII and -XII groups in coconut palms in Cuba.

- Locations in Cuba where the coconut plants were sampled.

■ THE TROPICSAFE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

Molecular identification of the coconut phytoplasmas

Symptomatic and asymptomatic coconut samples were collected from the most active disease *foci* located mainly in the north of the western and central region of the country. A sample from the south-eastern part of Cuba was also included. DNA extraction was performed from 1 g of trunk boring, using CTAB and/or phenol-chloroform based methods. Positive controls from lethal yellowing (16SrIV-A) infected palms from Mexico and Jamaica and 16SrIV-D from Mexico were used. PCR amplification was performed on 16S rRNA gene with universal primers, followed by nested PCR with general and 16SrIV group specific primers and RFLP and /or sequencing. Moreover, the samples positive for 16SrIV were also amplified on the *groEL* gene with primers groELF1/R1 in direct and groELF2/R2 (Myrie *et al.*, 2011) in nested PCR. RFLP analyses with *Tru1I* and *AluI* on 16S rRNA gene amplicons was performed for phytoplasma identification. *HinfI* enzyme was employed to digest the groELF2/R2 amplicons. Eight out of 16 trunk borings were positive for phytoplasmas and the sequencing confirmed the identity of the detected phytoplasmas as verified with the RFLP analyses.

- Top figure: polyacrylamide gel visualized under ultraviolet light after ethidium bromide staining of RFLP profiles of amplicons obtained from coconut samples with the enzymes listed at the bottom. Left, primers 16S503f/LY16Sr; right, primers groELF2/R2. Samples from Cuba: c, C7, d, C13 and e, C168; samples from Mexico 1, 16SrIV-D and 2, 16SrIV-A; samples from Jamaica a and b; P, marker phiX174 DNA digested with *HaeIII*. Bottom figure: phylogenetic tree obtained using Neighbour-Joining method conducted in MEGA6 showing the different phytoplasmas detected in palms in Cuba and in Jamaica in bold.

■ SCIENTIFIC DATA AND FIRST RESULTS

Molecular diversity of phytoplasmas detected in coconut palms

The results indicate the presence of different phytoplasma ribosomal groups in palms. The 16SrIV strains detected were enclosed in the subgroup -A, while the RFLP on *groel* gene, not amplifying the phytoplasmas enclosed in the 16SrIV-D subgroup, showed that the phytoplasmas in one of the samples from Cuba is identical to the strains from Jamaica. In agreement with previous studies the predominant phytoplasma group detected was 16SrIV. However, strains in 16SrI, -VII and -XII groups were identified by RFLP analyses on 16S ribosomal gene and resulted clustering with phytoplasmas enclosed in these groups. These results indicated for the first time the occurrence of these phytoplasma groups in coconut palms affected with lethal yellowing in Cuba, some of them were already reported in coconut palms in other infected areas (Contaldo *et al.*, 2019).

Sample	Location/ Province	Phytoplasma ribosomal group
C4	Moronta, Camagüey	16SrVII
C6	La Gloria, Camagüey	16SrIV, 16SrXII
C7	Sola, Camagüey	16SrIV
C8		16SrIV
C9	St. Lucia, Camagüey	16SrI
C10		16SrXII
C13	Mayabeque	16SrIV
C168	Pilón Granma	16SrIV

- Results of the survey for phytoplasma detection.

KEY WORDS

Coconut, lethal yellowing disease, phytoplasmas, molecular identification

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GRAPEVINE

GRAPEVINE YELLOWS

■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Economic importance of a sector rich in cultural and traditional values

One of the aims of TROPICSAFE is to evaluate the impact of the solutions proposed to manage grapevine yellows, the phytoplasma-associated diseases considered one of the most important of the world grapevine sector. Given the importance of viticulture in traditional areas and the entry of new wine-growing countries into the global market, the development of specific disease management strategies, and the introduction of innovative solutions to detect and monitor its associated pathogens, are highly relevant. The analysis of grapevine sector in Chile, Italy and South Africa considers and compares economic and social aspects, such as production, acreage, yields and/or import-export (data of the International Organization of Vine and Wine, OIV). In these three countries, viticulture has a long tradition, it is a part of the landscape (such as the Prosecco area in Italy, recognized by the UNESCO world heritage list) and the cultivation of grapevines plays an important economic role, not in terms of surface, but especially in terms of production and export of wine.

- Vineyards in Italy (Conegliano and Valdobbiadene, Prosecco wine producing areas, Unesco's world heritage) (N. Simboli).

■ LATEST RESEARCH RESULTS

The importance of grapevine production

Grapevine (*Vitis* spp.) is a major crop, which has a worldwide high socioeconomic importance, but is also susceptible to several diseases, like yellows. According to the OIV data (estimates), in 2019 the total surface cultivated with grapevine in the world reached 7.4 million ha (-0.1% compared to 2018), with a global wine production of 260 million hl (-7%). Despite this negative variation, the world wine consumption slightly increased, reaching 244 million hl compared to 2018 (+0.1%). The United States of America confirms their first position in the ranking of consumers, followed by France and Italy.

In Europe, a positive trend in wine consumption is estimated for Italy, Spain and Germany, while France has experimented a slight decrease. The total export of wine in 2019 was 106 million hl (+1.7% compared to 2018). In terms of volume, the biggest exporters are Italy, Spain and France that together exported 571 million hl, 54% of the world market. Positive variations have been recorded in Italy (+10%), Spain (+7%), New Zealand (+5%), Chile (+3%). A decrease in export volumes in 2019 was observed in Australia (-13%) and South Africa (-24%). The global market value amounts to 31.8 billion euros. France, Italy and Spain are the main exporters also in terms of value in 2019 (9.8, 6.4 and 2.7 billion euros respectively), accounting for 60% of the total value of wine exported in 2019. France, Italy and Spain are the main exporters also in terms of value in 2019, with 9.8 billions euros, 6.4 billions euros and 2.7 billions euros respectively. These three countries account for 60% of the total value of wine exported in 2019. Compared to 2018, an increase in value with respect to 2018 was recorded in New Zealand (+8.3%), France (+4.6%), Italy (+3.4%), Portugal (+2.5%), Chile (+2.1%), Argentina (+1.2). A decrease in value of exports was recorded in South Africa (-11.0%), Spain (-8.0%) and Germany (-0.5%).

- Presence of different species of '*Candidatus Phytoplasma*' associated with grapevine yellows in the world (Assunta Bertaccini, unpublished).

■ THE TROPICSAFE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

New entries in the global market next to the traditional wine-producing countries

Chile: The grapevine sector in this country has had a great development in the last 20 years and nowadays Chile can be considered as one of the key players in the international wine scene, dominated traditionally by European countries. According to OIV data, during the period 1995-2017 the total surface devoted to vineyards increased, reaching the extension of 213,452 ha in 2017 (+74.8%; decreased in 2018 compared to 2017: -0.1%) with a production of grapes of almost 2 million tons (+30.8%; increased in 2018: +25%). The growth in vineyards has been followed by the development of the processing phase: in 2017 the production of wine is 9.5 million hl (+200% compared to 1995; increased in 2018: +36%), which feed the global export, estimated at 9.4 million hl (-1% in 2018), six times more than the value recorded in 1995.

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Italy: Viticulture in Italy has a long tradition. The country has a leading position thanks to a productive and diversified viticulture, characterized by a vast reserve of native grapevine varieties, the development of nursery activities, and the competitive prices of the products in the market. Following the European general trend, in Italy the area under grapevine cultivation and the production are decreasing: the data from 2017 shows an area of 696,649 ha (-24.9% compared to 1995; increased in 2018 compared to 2017: +0.9%), producing 6.9 million tons of grapes (-18.8%; increased in 2018: +25%). The production of wine is 42.5 million hl in 2017 (-23.7% compared to 1995; increased in 2018: +29%), however, Italy maintains its key role in the international market, with a strengthening in the export of wine (+35.3%: decreased in 2018: -7%).

South Africa: Together with Chile, South Africa is one of the new entries in the international market of wine. Vineyards are increasing in the country (the average in 2017 was 127,554 ha, +23.8% compared to 1995; decreased in 2018: -2%) and also the production of grapes (2 million tons; +52.3%; decreased in 2018: -10%) and wine (10.8 million hl, +29.5%; decreased in 2018: -12%). The development of internal production has had an impact on the international market, with a significant growth in the quantity of wine exported (from 0.7 million in 1995 to 4.5 million hl in 2017, increased in 2018: +18%) and imported (mainly from France, Italy and Portugal).

- Quantity of wine exported in Chile, Italy and South Africa (1,000 hl, 1995-2017) (OIV database 1995-2017).

■ SCIENTIFIC DATA AND FIRST RESULTS

Socioeconomic impact of grapevine yellows

Grapevine yellows can be considered the most important disease of *Vitis vinifera*, detected in several viticultural areas of the world. This disease, which involves several '*Candidatus Phytoplasma*' species, is characterized by similar symptoms, but different associated agents and epidemiological cycles. The phytoplasma associated with "flavescence dorée" occurs in all the major wine-producing areas of the Mediterranean countries and the phytoplasma is a quarantine organism. Severe crop losses have been attributed also to the phytoplasma associated with the "bois noir" disease. Outbreak of phytoplasma epidemics could be a risk in the vineyard agroecosystems, leading to negative economic impacts, more or less serious, depending on the severity of the infections since the life time of the diseased vineyards is reduced, and the quality of wine could be compromised by high acid and low sugar contents of fruiting clusters.

A vineyard is no longer economically viable when its productive plants are less than 25% of the total (CABI, 2013). This can happen when grapevine yellows are present. In Italy, the most damaging grapevine phytoplasma epidemics exploded in all the Northern area, starting from the beginning of the '80s. In Chile, the rapid expansion of the acreage and production resulted in a variable spreading of the diseases, that is associated with several phytoplasmas. No serious outbreaks have been reported in literature and the drop of Chilean production in the last years seems to be due to bad weather conditions or diversification of productions. The climate change is considered one of the most important concern for the development of grapevine sector also in South Africa (Vink *et al.*, 2010) where the epidemic outbreak of phytoplasmas in grapevine is associated only with the presence of '*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*'.

- Production of grapevine in Chile, South Africa and Italy (tons) (FAO DB 1961-2019).

KEY WORDS

Grapevine, wine, vineyards, phytoplasmas, diseases

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Update on phytoplasmas detected in grapevines

In the different viticultural areas in the world, phytoplasmas cause losses that range from 13 up to 100%, depending mainly on the virulence of the pathogen and the varietal susceptibility. Control is essentially based on the prevention of spread of the pathogen. The most efficient management tools are, therefore, the use of phytoplasma-free propagation material, the control of insect vectors and the elimination of inoculum sources of the pathogen, including alternate host plants. With this aim the identification of phytoplasmas present in the vineyards is of the highest priority and importance in order to focus the disease management efforts in the countries involved in the project. This will provide the appropriate information about target insect vectors to control and alternate host plants to eliminate in order to reduce the presence of the pathogen and also the pesticide usage.

- Symptoms in leaves of five grapevine samples positive for phytoplasmas in Chile. A) VN17- variety Chardonnay with downward rolling and yellowing of the veins. B) VN12- variety País with downward rolling and yellowing. C) VN29- variety Tintorera with downward rolling and reddening. D) VN69- variety Semillón with downward rolling and small leaves. E) Leaf of VN32- variety Sauvignon blanc with downward rolling and deformation.

■ LATEST RESEARCH RESULTS

What is known about the identity of phytoplasmas associated with grapevine yellows in Chile, Italy and South Africa?

The grapevine yellows agents are generally well known in Europe, while less data and information are available for other countries, such as Chile and South Africa. In South Africa the agent and its main insect vector have been discovered, while in Chile different grapevine phytoplasmas and insects harbouring some of these phytoplasmas have been identified. In the majority of the European countries, the phytoplasmas associated with the disease are known as “bois noir” and “flavescence dorée”, the last one being a quarantine organism (Angelini *et al.*, 2018). The surveys in Italy allowed the detection of new phytoplasmas and new potential insect vectors in some of the main grapevine growing regions (Zambon *et al.*, 2018). It is therefore clear that only a constant monitoring will allow the prompt detection of reported phytoplasmas or new phytoplasmas that may infect grapevine plants. Furthermore, monitoring is necessary to determine if the endemic phytoplasmas are spreading. This information is the basis for control measures. Finally, knowledge of the phytoplasma strains associated with grapevine yellows in the three countries is necessary for improving the detection techniques.

- Areas in South Africa where the '*Candidatus* Phytoplasma asteris' associated with grapevine yellows has been identified.

- Italian areas where new phytoplasmas associated with grapevine yellows were detected.

- Chilean regions surveyed and locations where the phytoplasmas were detected in the vineyards.

■ THE TROPICSAFE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

Techniques for the molecular identification of the grapevine yellows phytoplasmas

Samples from grapevine grown commercially in affected areas within the three countries were collected during the summer/autumn seasons in 2017 and 2018 and stored at -80°C for subsequent testing. The presence of phytoplasmas was detected after nucleic acid extraction and polymerase chain reaction (PCR) followed by restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) and sequencing. The primers used for the PCR amplification are given in Table 1 for the three areas, Table 2 for Chile and Table 3 for Italy and South Africa.

In Chile, the survey was carried out in the Maule and Valparaiso Regions. Ninety samples were collected and analysed by nested PCR using 50S ribosomal subunit gene primers, designed by the "Laboratorio de Fitovirología" of the University of Chile (Table 2). The amplification products from four samples were sequenced to identify the phytoplasmas present. Results were confirmed using nested PCR with P1/P7 primers, followed by R16F2n/R2 primers (Table 1). In Italy, total nucleic acids were extracted with a chloroform/phenol method from symptomatic grapevine samples collected in diverse areas and used in PCR assays with the same protocol just described before. Additional nested-PCR assays were carried out using primers R16(I)F1/R1 (Table 3). Phytoplasma identity was detected by RFLP analyses. Selected samples were then sequenced to confirm phytoplasma identity

by virtual RFLP and phylogeny. In South Africa, sampling was carried out in the white cultivar Colombard. Samples from asymptomatic and symptomatic plants were collected and processed by removing phloem tissues from which DNA was extracted using a CTAB-based protocol. The extracted DNA was quantified by nanodrop analysis and quality parameters for the samples ranged between A260/280: 1.73-2.02 and A260/230: 0.80-1.86, while concentrations ranged from 69 to 352 ng/ μ L. The DNA quality was further assessed by agarose gel electrophoresis. The aster yellows phytoplasma diagnostics were performed using the PCR assay reported in Table 3.

Table 1. General primers used for Phytoplasma detection in grapevine in Chile, Italy and South Africa

Assay	Primer set	Amplicon size (bp)	Literature
PCR	P1/P7	1,792	Deng and Hiruki, 1991; Schneider <i>et al.</i> , 1995;
PCR nested 1	R16F2n / R16R2	1,244	Gunderser and Lee, 1996;
PCR nested 2	U5/U3	800	Lorenz <i>et al.</i> , 1995.

Table 2. General primers used for phytoplasma detection in grapevine in Chile

Assay	Primer set	Amplicon size (bp)	Literature
PCR	LSu2pF / LSu2pR	1,700	Zamorano and Fiore, unpublished.
PCR nested	LSu2pFn / LSu2pRn	1,280	

Table 3. Primers used for phytoplasma detection in grapevine in Italy and South Africa

Assay	Primer set	Amplicon size (bp)	Literature
PCR	P1/P7	1,792	Deng and Hiruki, 1991; Schneider <i>et al.</i> , 1995;
PCR nested 1	R16F2n / R16R2	1,244	Gunderser and Lee, 1996;
PCR nested 2	R16(I)F1 / R16(I)R1	1,100	Lee <i>et al.</i> , 1995.

■ SCIENTIFIC DATA AND FIRST RESULTS

Identification of phytoplasmas associated with grapevine yellows diseases

The surveys carried out in the three countries confirmed the presence of diverse prevalent phytoplasmas. In Chile the samples examined were infected with a '*Candidatus Phytoplasma pruni*'-related strain classified in the 16SrIII-J subgroup; with a '*Ca. P. ulmi*'-related strain (16SrV-A); a '*Ca. P. fraxini*'-related strain (16SrVII-A); and a '*Ca. P. solani*'-related strain (16SrXII-A). The situation in Chile, with the constant presence of these phytoplasmas in the surveyed vineyards, remained unchanged. In Italy the main phytoplasmas detected were '*Ca. P. solani*'-related and '*Ca. P. asteris*'-related (16SrI-B). Others phytoplasmas were also detected: '*Ca. P. fraxini*'-related (16SrVII-A); "flavescence dorée" (16SrV-C and -D); '*Ca. P. trifolii*'-related (16SrVI); '*Ca. P. phoenicium*'-related (16SrIX); '*Ca. P. pruni*'-related (16SrIII); '*Ca. P. prunorum*'-related (16SrX-B). Samples with mixed infection with two of these phytoplasmas have also been recorded. The increasing presence of '*Ca. P. asteris*'-related phytoplasma needs monitoring through specific detection tools application in order to be able to manage the possible epidemic increasing of the dissemination of the phytoplasma. In South Africa the presence of '*Ca. P. asteris*'-related strains (16SrI-B and 16SrI-C) was confirmed in the areas where the disease was first reported, confirming the severity of the presence of this phytoplasma associated with the grapevine yellows disease.

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- Virtual restriction fragment length polymorphism analyses on grapevine R16F2n/R2 amplicon (GenBank accession number KY454858) and reference strains using the interactive online tool *iPhyClassifier* (from Zambon *et al.*, 2018).

KEY WORDS

Nested-PCR, RFLP, phytoplasmas identification, phytoplasma control

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TRANSMISSION OF PHYTOPLASMAS BY LEAFHOPPERS IN CHILE

Paratanus exitiosus and *Bergallia valdiviana* are able to transmit the 16SrIII-J phytoplasma

■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Phytoplasma insect vectors in Chile

In Chile, grapevine yellows is associated with phytoplasmas belonging to diverse ribosomal subgroups. However, the phytoplasmas in the 16SrIII-J subgroup are prevalent in the vineyards of the country. This phytoplasma has been reported to infect various crops and spontaneous plant species. Phytoplasma dissemination in the field occurs with the use of infected plant materials and by insect vector transmission. The leafhoppers found in Chilean vineyards generally feed on weeds and only occasionally on grapevine, allowing the transmission of phytoplasmas to this species. In order to determine which insects are involved in transmission of the 16SrIII-J phytoplasma, an epidemiological study was carried out in symptomatic phytoplasma-infected vineyards. Transmission trials were carried out with two 16SrIII-J phytoplasma positive insects, *Paratanus exitiosus* and *Bergallia valdiviana*.

• Insect species used in transmission trials: A) *Paratanus exitiosus*; B) *Bergallia valdiviana*.

■ LATEST RESEARCH RESULTS

How to determine the phytoplasma transmission capacity by an insect?

Insects were collected in a phytoplasma infected vineyard. They were captured by means of an entomological sweeping net. Adults of *P. exitiosus* and *B. valdiviana* were divided in two batches and released into two entomological cages to let them feed on three grapevine plants cultivar Cabernet Sauvignon, and three periwinkle plants. For the transmission assays with *P. exitiosus*, 81 periwinkle and 81 grapevine plants were used. For the transmission trials with *B. valdiviana*, 27 periwinkle and 21 grapevine plants were used. All the plants were kept in a conditioned chamber. Each feeding period lasted until the death of all the insects released in a cage. Assays for phytoplasma detection in the plants used for the transmission trials were carried out every three months. All the leafhoppers from a single cage were also tested in order to confirm the phytoplasma presence in the insects.

- Survey of insects in vineyard using entomological sweeping net.

- Entomological cages used for the transmission trials (left) and insects on a periwinkle plant inside the entomological cage (right).

■ THE TROPICSAFE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

Phytoplasma identification in plants and insects used in transmission trials

The phytoplasma detection in the plants after the transmission trials was obtained after three to twelve months for periwinkle and one to two years for grapevine. The phytoplasma presence was detected in *P. exitiosus* and *B. valdiviana* specimens used for transmission assays. Five grapevine plants and three periwinkle plants from the *P. exitiosus* transmission trials resulted positive for phytoplasma 16SrIII-J. Two grapevine plants and two periwinkle plants used in the transmission trials with *B. valdiviana* were also positive for phytoplasma 16SrIII-J. *P. exitiosus* showed 4.97% and *B. valdiviana* 8.3% of transmission. The 16SrIII-J positive grapevine plants showed short internodes, and leaves with downward rolling, deformation, yellowing and necrosis, twenty-four months after the start of the transmission trials. The 16SrIII-J infected periwinkle plants showed witches' broom, virescence, leaf

deformation and severe yellowing, five to fifteen months after the start of the transmission trials. All the results were verified by nested PCR of the 16S rRNA and *tuf* genes, sequence and RFLP analyses (Quiroga *et al.*, 2019).

- Symptoms in periwinkle (above) and grapevine (below) after *P. exitiosus* and *B. valdiviana* transmission; A) flowers with virescence; B) flowers with virescence and phyllody; C) plant with witches' broom, small and yellow leaves; D) leaves with downward rolling and deformation; E) short internodes.

■ SCIENTIFIC DATA AND FIRST RESULTS

Implications of phytoplasma vectors insect's determination in Chile

Both insects live on weeds and only occasionally feed on grapevine or other crops. *P. exitiosus* has more abundant populations during spring and summer, while *B. valdiviana* has high populations during late summer, autumn and early winter. This could play a fundamental role in maintaining the phytoplasma population in the weeds during the vegetative recess of the grapevine. The phytoplasma 16SrIII-J and its newly identified insect vectors are widely distributed in Chile on different weed species and crops of agronomic interest (Hepp and Vargas, 2002; González *et al.*, 2011; Longone *et al.*, 2011). Taking into account the *P. exitiosus* and *B. valdiviana* transmission rates observed, if environmental conditions are favourable, there is a high likelihood to expect an outbreak of grapevine yellows

in Chile due to 16SrIII-J phytoplasmas. The climate change could modify the habitat of these insects as well as increase their reproduction rate in the central zone of Chile (Quiroga *et al.*, 2017). The information that has been generated through this investigation allows to generate management plans for grapevine yellows in Chile.

KEY WORDS

Phytoplasma, Auchenorrhyncha, transmission trials.

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Problems and losses due to grapevine yellows diseases in the world

Grapevine cultivation and grapevine and wine industry worldwide are seriously threatened by yellows diseases associated with the presence of different phytoplasmas, which are present with diverse prevalence in all the grape growing countries. Damages in grapevine associated with the presence of yellows diseases spans from a lower yield of berries to the death of the plants. The management strategies available are mainly based on uprooting symptomatic infected plants and on the use of insecticides to reduce the number of the known insect vectors. However, towards a more sustainable agriculture, these methods should be flanked by the development of resistant grapevine varieties. The identification of the candidate resistance is therefore a great aid in the development of management tools for grapevine yellows control and will help to reduce both the economic damages and the insecticide treatments worldwide.

- Symptoms of grapevine yellows disease in the bunch of a red variety at the beginning of the summer.

■ LATEST RESEARCH RESULTS

Available data on grapevine yellows resistance

Intraspecific variability in *Vitis vinifera* susceptibility to grapevine yellows is well known from field experience, while only a few data were obtained in controlled conditions of inoculation (Eveillard *et al.*, 2016). On the basis of these observations, some molecular studies aimed to identify grapevine genetic traits involved in the response to grapevine yellows infection were carried out in the last few years. Qualitative and quantitative changes in protein, gene expression and miRNA profiles were investigated in the Chardonnay and a few other varieties (Albertazzi *et al.*, 2009; Hren *et al.*, 2009; Margaria *et al.*, 2014; Snyman *et al.*, 2017). These

- Grapevine progenies (Chardonnay x Tocai friulano) planted in the field.

analyses were performed on healthy and infected plants in the field, thus revealing the effects of the disease on the different varieties having differences in their disease susceptibility. One of the last literature works reported the presence of an early transcriptomic response of the plant to the infection and to the insect vector, suggesting the existence of constitutively expressed passive defense mechanisms and active defense reactions of a very low susceptible variety, the Tocai friulano or Sauvignonasse (Bertazzon *et al.*, 2019). TROPICSAFE project aims to identify the genetic determinants of resistance in this variety.

■ THE TROPICSAFE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

Characterization of an F1 grapevine population segregating for grapevine yellows resistance

More than 700 grapevine plants were obtained by crossing Chardonnay (susceptible) with Tocai friulano (low susceptible). Part of the progenies was multiplied by grafting on SO4 rootstock and planted in an experimental vineyard (20 plants for genotype), while another part is currently under multiplication in nursery.

The subsequent work includes: phenotyping of the progenies, genotyping to obtain a dense genetic map based on SNP (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism) molecular markers, and joining of the data to infer QTLs (Quantitative Trait Loci) associated to grapevine yellows resistance. Phenotyping is obtained by controlled infection in the field by insect vectors. Cages were placed on each plant, containing 20 insect vectors collected from very infected vineyards. Symptoms (severity, prevalence) and concentration of the pathogen will be evaluated.

DNA was extracted from F1 plants and a preliminary screening was performed to check the parental origin of the seedlings (e.g. discarding those derived from selfing) by SSR (Simple Sequence Repeats) analysis with ten molecular markers. Genotyping the selected plants is in progress by GBS (Genotyping By Sequencing) for subsequent SNPs calling. A genetic map will be produced. from this data. Phenotypic and molecular information will be used to find QTLs associated with grapevine yellows resistance. Moreover, data integration with transcriptomic profiles obtained with RNAseq from low and very susceptible varieties, previously obtained (Bertazzon *et al.*, 2019) and full genome by Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) of approximately 20 grapevine varieties showing opposite behavior against the disease, will be the basis for the identification of the candidate genes associated to grapevine yellows resistance.

- Setting up of cages for insects in the single plants in the field (left), and detail of a cage (right). A cage containing 20 insect vectors was placed in every plant, in order to infect all the grapevine plants.

■ SCIENTIFIC DATA AND FIRST RESULTS

First results and perspectives

Obtainment of a sufficient number of progenies by breeding and their prosperous multiplication and plantation in the field was the first result. DNA was extracted from more than 300 genotypes, followed by screening with ten SSR markers to discriminate among crossed and self-crossed progeny. Results showed that approximately 20% of the progeny was self-crossed, thus these plants were discarded.

The nucleotide sequencing work started with DNA extraction from leaf samples of 208 plants, including the two parents Tocai friulano and Chardonnay. After DNA extracts evaluation for quality and quantity, a total of 188 samples were sent to sequencing by GBS to obtain a high-density genetic map.

In 2019 a total of 140 plants were caged with infective insects. At the end of the work, the identification of genetic traits associated to resistance and susceptibility to grapevine yellows could be exploited to generate grapevine plants resistant to this disease and for increasing or eliciting the grapevine yellows resistance in plants.

• Genetic analyzer electrotraces. Example of 10 *loci* multiplex PCR molecular profile used to identify crossed or self-crossed progeny by SSR. The 10 primer pairs were labeled with NED(a), 6-FAM (b), PET (c), VIC (d) dyes. Grey stripes represent the home-made binset produced with reference varieties.

KEY WORDS

Grapevine yellows, resistance, tolerance, “flavescence dorée”, “bois noir”, breeding, disease

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Lack of well-characterized and certified material for use as phytoplasma reference positive control

The important economic sector of world grapevine production of 74 million tons is threatened by several grapevine yellows diseases associated with the presence of phytoplasmas. There is a lack of availability of well-characterized and certified material suitable for use as reference positive controls in different diagnostic schemes, validation studies, performance studies and proficiency tests, which are all part of the management programs for fast and accurate detection of grapevine yellows phytoplasmas.

'*Candidatus Phytoplasma solani*' associated with "bois noir", the most widespread disease of grapevine in the Euro-Mediterranean basin, was selected as a model. In the last 20 years, "bois noir" has become a major limiting factor in the European viticulture, which seriously affects quality and quantity of grapevine production with infection rates reaching 50–80% in some areas. In South Africa grapevine yellows is associated with the presence of '*Ca. P. asteris*' while in Chile and in the other countries several diverse phytoplasmas are present. Molecular methods are needed to detect '*Ca. P. solani*' or '*Ca. P. asteris*' in low concentrations and in many samples and quantitative PCR is a commonly used method. It gives a numerical result which reflects the concentration of the target in the sample. However, these numerical values also depend on the specific reagents, their concentrations and the instrument used. Thus the results obtained in different laboratories are not directly comparable. A reference material can be used as a fixed point in all the studies and research making the results directly comparable among laboratories and, even more importantly, over the time. Certified reference materials are not available for plant pathogens. To overcome this difficulty, two types of reference materials for some of the phytoplasmas of grapevine were prepared.

• Transmission electron microscope picture of cross-section of a midrib of symptomatic *Catharanthus roseus* infected with '*Ca. P. solani*' (Photo: M. Tušek Žnidarič).

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Two reference materials for a grapevine phytoplasma

Two types of reference materials have been prepared:

- 1) DNA sequences of the target region used for the quantitative PCR originally described by Hren *et al.* (2007), together with nucleotide data available in NCBI, were used for designing synthetic DNA, e.g. gBlocks, IDT. Synthetic double-stranded DNA of known size and amount is cheap and provides high amounts of the specific sequence target suitable for technical assessment of tests and as a positive control for testing,
- 2) DNA from grapevine naturally infected with '*Ca. P. solani*' was selected and protocols for its quantification by digital droplet PCR were designed for assigning reference values to the concentration of target sequences. This method enables absolute quantification without the need for standards and calibration.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Publically available sequence data and characterization of material with digital droplet PCR

Preparation of reference material is a challenging process requiring high accuracy, and it is particularly difficult, demanding and time consuming since the growth of phytoplasmas in artificial media is still not a routine method. The two types of reference materials prepared during the TROPICSAFE project are the prerequisites for further studies of grapevine infected with either 'Ca. P. solani' or 'Ca. P. asteris' that require reference positive test controls. Both approaches for preparation of reference material are easily transferrable to other phytoplasmas and DNA targets. Moreover, they have been applied to assigned values to reference materials used in international proficiency tests organized by the National Institute of Biology in Slovenia for a number of different pathogens.

The first reference material is based on the synthetic double-stranded DNA, for which the publically available sequence data were used. The known size and amount allows preparation of material with relatively well-defined target concentration without additional testing.

The second reference material, more similar to the diagnostic samples, is based on DNA samples from grapevine leaf veins infected with 'Ca. P. solani'. Reference values of target sequence concentrations were assigned after the characterization of the material with digital droplet PCR, a gold standard method for absolute quantification.

```
> gBlock control on KT281865.1 Candidatus Phytoplasma solani isolate STOL3 1-acyl-sn-glycerol-3-phosphate acyltransferase gene, partial cds
ACGTAAAACAGCTTTAAGTTTAATAAAAGGCAATTCCTCAAAGTAAAAGCAGGTTTAGCGGATG
GTTGTTTTCTGGAAGGTGGTATTAAGATCGAAATGATGAAGCAACGGTACCACTTTTAG
AGGGGTCTTTTAAAATTGCTTTTAAAACGCAAGCCGA
```

- Sequence of the proposed synthetic DNA control for the 'Ca. P. solani' amplicon targeted by qPCR. Shaded areas correspond to primer and probe annealing sites, the sites recognized by the reagents used to detect the pathogen.

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Potential of reference positive test controls and their transfer to other phytoplasmas and DNA targets

In a synthetic DNA reference material a potential drawback is that the synthesized DNA is target specific and therefore a test specific sequence; its known size and amount allow preparation of material with relatively well defined target concentration without additional testing. Based on the selected target sequence this reference material can be ordered commercially, which is an important advantage of this approach.

The plant material naturally infected with 'Ca. P. solani' was characterized by digital droplet PCR (ddPCR) as a higher quality method in metrological and clinical fields for absolute quantification of target concentrations without the need for calibration. For the preparation of reference material, a current qPCR protocol was successfully transferred to the ddPCR format and used to determine absolute concentration of the target DNA copies in the samples. The protocol can be used to assign values to naturally infected samples or artificially prepared defined mixtures.

Either of the two types of reference material described here are fit for the purpose. A reference material with a known target concentration provides comparability over the tests and, more importantly, over the time as it can be repeatedly prepared with the same characteristics. The described approach is transferrable to other phytoplasmas and DNA targets.

	Synthetic dsDNA (gBlock™)	Naturally infected samples
P	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> high amounts of target sequence DNA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> similar to the diagnostic samples
R	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> well defined target concentration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> more commutable
O	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> commercially available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> can be used in a variety of molecular tests
S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> comparable over tests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> provides information on the influence of DNA isolation
C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> sequence specific 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> limited amounts and availability
O	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DNA isolation not needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DNA isolation needed
N		
S		

- Characteristics of the two types of reference materials prepared for the 'Ca. P. solani' agent associated with the "bois noir" disease.

KEY WORDS

Reference material, detection, plant pathogen, digital droplet PCR

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SEROLOGICAL TESTS TO DETECT GRAPEVINE YELLOW PHYTOPLASMAS

Set up friendly detection methods for identification of selected phytoplasmas associated with grapevine yellows

■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Improved tools for monitoring grapevine yellows presence

Grapevine yellows are severe diseases associated with several phytoplasmas, insect vectors, and host plants, widespread in different grapevine cultivation regions. Collectively, “flavescence dorée”, “bois noir” and aster yellows, are considered as a complex disease model based on multiple variables (phytoplasma, host plants and insect vectors), each behaving often differently in diverse ecosystems. So far, the detection of grapevine yellows phytoplasmas has relied on a set of molecular techniques that target the genome of the pathogen. Even though these techniques are sound and reliable, the diagnostic scheme is relatively expensive and lacks suitability for large scale monitoring methods. Serological tests were therefore evaluated under the TROPICSAFE activities to overcome the scarcity of the antigenic protein, assess the test sensitivity when the pathogen is present at low titer and compare their specificity to the results obtained with phytoplasma molecular identification.

• Grapevine yellows infected plants.

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Raising phytoplasma-specific antibodies

To overcome the scarcity of the phytoplasma antigenic proteins, the TROPICSAFE activities were focused on culturing grapevine aster yellows phytoplasmas in artificial medium and developing the synthesis of “flavescence dorée” antigenic proteins using a bacterium expression system. Both technologies allowed the production of antigenic preparations suitable for producing specific antibodies against the two phytoplasmas. These antibodies are now available for designing new serological tests to complement the molecular phytoplasma detection.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Development of serological tests

The antibodies were evaluated for serological applications, giving a priority to low-cost techniques routinely applied in the grapevine testing laboratories for other pathogens.

The grapevine aster yellows antibodies were applied to the immunofluorescence antibody assay (IFAS), a technique routinely applied to detect bacteria. A sound enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) could be developed for “flavescence dorée” phytoplasmas: the protocol was challenged for its diagnostic performances by comparison with quantitative PCR test. Moreover, this ELISA was evaluated by testing a whole range of samples including grapevine leaves, insect vectors, and alternative host plant species. The assessment of the diagnostic performances (specificity and sensitivity) was addressed by a double check based on molecularly identified samples.

- On the left: colonies containing grapevine aster yellows phytoplasmas growing in solid medium photographed under bifocal microscopy at 40 X used as antigenic preparation. On the right: Western blot analysis of IgG anti “flavescence dorée” strain 16SrV-D recombinant protein (from Trivellone *et al.*, 2019).

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Testing grapevine yellows antibodies

The ELISA test was proven to be a reliable tool to specifically detect the “flavescence dorée” phytoplasma presence in symptomatic grapevine plants. It works also for testing the main insect vector *Scaphoideus titanus*, and *Alnus glutinosa* and *Clematis vitalba* alternative host plants. Along three years of field sampling, two “flavescence dorée”-ELISA tests, targeting two diverse strains, were shown to be 100% strain specific in ELISA and were confirmed as reliable by qPCR. The exclusion of cross reactions among known strains makes the test suitable for one-step strain identification. The specificity values ranged from 80% to 100%, depending on the sample (plant or insect), while the preliminary assessment revealed a diagnostic sensitivity ranging from 58% to 64%. Even though the sensitivity values seem to be critical, this ELISA test might be used in the monitoring programs as a preliminary screening of a large number of samples; the samples resulting negative can then be tested by more sensitive molecular methods such as qPCR. The application of this protocol will produce about 50% reduction of costs for large screening programs.

Furthermore grapevine aster yellows antibodies were tested by ELISA and IFAS methods to evaluate their suitability for phytoplasma detection in plant samples. The two methods showed a good specificity to the aster yellows phytoplasma cultures, while the IFAS assay gave promising results also with infected plant tissues.

- Top from left: grapevine samples and *Scaphoideus titanus* adult for “flavescence dorée” ELISA test. Bottom from left: ELISA results for “flavescence dorée” and IFAS grapevine aster yellows detection of healthy periwinkle, cultivated aster yellows phytoplasma, aster yellows infected periwinkle tissue (from Contaldo *et al.*, 2019).

KEY WORDS

Antiserum production, “flavescence dorée”, aster yellows, serological detection.

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Grapevine yellows: impact and symptomatology

The important economic sector of annual world grape production of 74 million tonnes is threatened by several grapevine yellows diseases associated the presence of phytoplasma. In the Euro-Mediterranean basin this has become a major limiting factor in viticulture, seriously affecting the quality and quantity of grapevine production, with infection rates reaching 50% to 80%. While in Europe and in Chile several diverse phytoplasmas have been detected in grapevine yellows infected plants, in South Africa, the disease is mainly associated with the presence of '*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*' (16SrI-B). Although the phytoplasmas involved are diverse, mainly according to geographical distribution, the disease symptoms are similar. The epidemiology of grapevine yellows is complex. It involves alternative plant hosts that have important roles as reservoirs from which the insect vectors can transmit the phytoplasmas to grapevines. Phytoplasma insect vectors are primarily leafhoppers, planthoppers and psyllids. Although the alternative hosts and insect vector species for many of these phytoplasmas remain unknown, the advantage of their identification in a given pathosystem is that it allows their targeted removal, reducing both the infected material and the labour costs, as well as the environmental impact of the disease.

- Main symptoms in grapevine include irregular yellowing or reddening in white and red cultivars, respectively, downward curling very often with a triangle shape of the leaves, shortened internodes, death of tips and shoots, lack of lignification, aborting flowers, shrivelling and early drying of berries.

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Knowing symptomatology it the first step towards an appropriate grapevine yellows management strategy

Grapevine yellows management methods include rouging symptomatic grapevines and control host-plant reservoirs and insect vectors. In vineyards, the typical grapevine yellows symptoms observed are downward rolling of leaves; reddening or yellowing of leaves and leaf veins; incomplete shoot lignification; drying up of bunches; plant decline.

The most important variety infected by phytoplasmas in Chile are Thompson Seedless, Crimson Seedless and Autumn Royal (table grape); Cabernet Sauvignon, Pinot noir, Sauvignon blanc, Petit Syrah, Merlot, Carménère, Chardonnay and Syrah (wine grape). The symptoms observed in different combinations of grapevine varieties and phytoplasmas are very similar, and minor differences are probably related to the variety susceptibility, age of the plant, the presence of other pathogens, and the action of biotic and abiotic agents causing root damage. A particular situation is represented by the drying up of bunches that occurs in several varieties that, especially in Petit Syrah and Merlot, is associated with considerable product losses. In South Africa aster yellows in symptomatic plants, such as Chardonnay and Colombard, include also leaves with a wrinkled appearance that turn downwards and are thicker than usual, short internodes, shoots that do not lignify and growth tips that may die back. In Europe and South Africa the main infected variety is Chardonnay but, according to local varieties, a very few varieties result in no symptoms in the presence of epidemic phytoplasma spread.

While the recognition of grapevine yellows symptoms is feasible after some practice, searching for alternative plant hosts might involve additional molecular testing, because in many cases, plants that might represent latent sources of phytoplasmas do not show symptoms. Finding possible alternative insect vectors is even more demanding, and includes collection of the insects near an infected area, molecular determination of phytoplasma presence, and additional testing to demonstrate vector transmission.

The insect surveys are performed by collecting potential new vectors using yellow sticky traps or through an entomological sweeping net. After insect identification under binocular microscope with the help of expert insect taxonomists, when necessary, the insects are then tested for phytoplasma presence after DNA extraction applying nested-PCR with phytoplasma-specific primers. The potential new host plants are collected based on the presence of symptoms similar to those observed for known phytoplasma-infected plants.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Search for alternative plant hosts and potential insect vectors of grapevine yellows phytoplasmas

As grapevine yellows has been studied in the European areas for decades, the biology and epidemiology of the most frequently associated phytoplasmas (*Candidatus Phytoplasma solani*, 16SrXII-A and "flavescence dorée", 16SrV-C/-D) are well studied, and their main reservoir plants and insect vectors have been identified. However, changing environments and the recent introduction of several alien species of both potential phytoplasma insect vectors and weeds has increased the risk of spread of new phytoplasmas or new strains that might affect the sanitary status of the vineyards.

In Italy a survey conducted in the area of Treviso province (Prosecco wine), allowed to verify the presence of 14 alternative plant species for the three main phytoplasmas detected in the grapevine with yellows such as 16SrXII-A, 16SrI and 16SrV. The same survey allowed to verify the presence of new potential insect vector species and of

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diverse phytoplasmas in the known vector species (Table, in bold the new findings). The finding of aster yellows in *Hedera helix* is a new report on this species. The plant species infected with 16SrXII-A phytoplasma are confirming or increasing the list of the several host plant species harboring as possible source of infection this phytoplasma in vineyards and in several other agricultural and natural environments.

Insect species	Phytoplasma identified
<i>Hyalesthes obsoletus</i> Signoret	16Srl-B , 16SrXII-A
<i>Neoliturus fenestratus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1834)	16Srl , 16SrXII-A
<i>Orientus ishidae</i> Matsumura	16Srl-B , 16SrV-C, 16SrXII-A
<i>Scaphoideus titanus</i> (Ball)	16Srl-B , 16SrV-C, 16SrXII-A
Plant species	
<i>Calystegia sepium</i> (L.) R.Br.	16SrXII-A
<i>Clematis vitalba</i> L.	16SrV, 16Srl
<i>Convolvulus</i> spp.	16SrXII-A
<i>Conyza Canadensis</i> (L.) Cronq.	16SrXII-A
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> L.	16SrXII-A
<i>Hedera helix</i> L.	16Srl
<i>Morus</i> spp.	16Srl
<i>Parthenocissus quinquefolia</i> (L.) Planch.	16SrXII-A
<i>Quercus</i> spp.	16SrXII-A
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L.	16SrXII-A
<i>Rosa canina</i> L.	16SrXII-A
<i>Rubus</i> spp.	16Srl
<i>Rubus ulmifolius</i> Schott.	16SrXII-A
<i>Sorghum halepense</i> (L.) Pers.	16Srl

In South Africa the leafhopper *Mgenia fuscovaria* (Stål) is a vector of 'Ca. P. asteris' associated with grapevine yellows. Aster yellows phytoplasma was identified in two further leafhopper species, *Aconurella prolixa* and *Exitianus* sp. These phytoplasmas were also detected in the potential reservoir plants *Mesembryanthemum crystallinum* L., *Raphanus sativus* L. and *Protea cynaroides* L.

In Chile, among the captured insects, the phytoplasma 16SrIII-J, was detected only in *Paratanus exitiosus* (Beamer) and *Bergallia valdiviana* Berg. The transmission trials, performed in periwinkle and grapevine plants, corroborated that these two insect species are vectors of the phytoplasma 16SrIII-J. The same phytoplasma was also found in *Polygonum aviculare* L. and *Convolvulus arvensis* L., growing in infected vineyards. During the project, in the vineyards infected by the phytoplasma 16SrIII-J, the sampling of alternative host plants and potential insect vectors has continued.

• Top from left: plants of *M. crystallinum* (https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eiskraut#/media/Datei:Xer_mesemb.jpg) and *M. caryophyllacea* [[https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Montinia_caryophyllacea#/media/Datei:Montinia_caryophyllacea_\(Montiniaceae\)_\(23854745238\).jpg](https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Montinia_caryophyllacea#/media/Datei:Montinia_caryophyllacea_(Montiniaceae)_(23854745238).jpg)] species were sometimes infected with 'Ca. P. asteris' in South Africa. The grass-feeding leafhopper *Aconeurella prolixa* [M. Stiller (Agricultural Research Council - Plant Health and Protection, National Collection of Insects)] tested positive for 'Ca. P. asteris' and successfully transmitted it to an artificial feeding medium and to wheat plants. Bottom from left: weeds *Polygonum aviculare* and *Convolvulus arvensis* in Chilean vineyards and positive to the phytoplasmas 16SrIII-J.

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

New possible grapevine phytoplasma host plants and their insect vectors are moved to a new trial phase

During TROPICSAFE, the surveys of new alternative host plants of grapevine phytoplasmas, together with possible insect vectors of these phytoplasmas, revealed a long list of different species. The infected plants in the proximity of vineyards were collected mostly upon inspection for clear phytoplasma symptoms. However, it is highly possible that the phytoplasma infection could be latent, and not all infected plants express symptoms. In such cases, the infection remains a hidden reservoir with the potential for further spread the disease. Therefore, it is recommended to test the most widespread weeds and other plants near vineyards for possible infections.

TROPICSAFE also demonstrated that some leafhoppers and planthoppers were infected with grapevine yellows phytoplasmas. Although the presence of the phytoplasmas was confirmed, their mere presence in an insect is not proof of vector status, which needs to be additionally tested using feeding medium experiments and transmission of phytoplasmas to grapevines under controlled conditions.

In Chile, five previously unreported plant species resulted positive for one of the main phytoplasmas associated with grapevine yellows the 16SrIII-J phytoplasma (*Rosa* spp., *Brassica rapa* L., *Erodium* spp., *Malva* spp. and *Rubus ulmifolius* Schott) and five insect species were fully or partially identified (*Amplicephalus ornatus* Linnavuori, *A. pallidus* Linnavuori, *A. curtulus* Linnavuori & DeLong, *Bergallia* sp., *Exitianus obscurinervis* Stål) as potential vectors of the same phytoplasma.

- 16SrIII-J phytoplasma-positive leafhopper species: (A) *Bergallia* sp.; (B) *Amplicephalus ornatus*; (C) *A. curtulus*; (D) *A. pallidus*; (E) *Exitianus obscurinervis*. Symptoms in weeds and shrubs infected with 16SrIII-J phytoplasma: (F) corky leaves in *Malva* spp.; (G) deformation and corky texture of leaves in *Brassica rapa*; (H, I) *Rubus ulmifolius* showing witches' broom and leaves deformation; (L, M) witches' broom, leaves and floral tip deformation in *Rosa* sp. Bottom row: yellow sticky traps to collect insects in Chilean vineyards.

KEY WORDS

Grapevine yellows, phytoplasmas, symptomatology, alternative host plants, insect vectors.

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THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Diversity of phytoplasmas detected in grapevine plants

The descriptions of severe epidemics of grapevine yellows in Italy date back to the 1990s, when severe losses mainly due to the presence of “flavescence dorée” were reported especially in the northern regions. In the following years in other regions the presence of “bois noir” and erratically of other phytoplasmas was also described. The economic impact of the grapevine yellows disease had been under control over the past 20 years, until recently scattered outbreaks and localized epidemics started to re-emerge. Surveys were carried out in the frame of the TROPICSAFE project in selected Italian vineyards located in Veneto, Emilia-Romagna, Tuscany, Marche, and Abruzzo regions and performed by sequencing the 16S ribosomal RNA gene of phytoplasmas amplified by specific polymerase chain reaction (PCR) or nested-PCR. The testing allowed identification of the presence of ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma solani*’, ‘*Ca. P. fraxini*’, ‘*Ca. P. prunorum*’, ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ and other ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma*’ species that were erratically present. Moreover, in Veneto and Emilia-Romagna regions diverse strains of “flavescence dorée” phytoplasmas were identified by multigenic molecular testing followed by sequencing and/or restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) analyses. As occurs worldwide, the main infected variety was Chardonnay, but several other popular varieties such as Sangiovese, Lambrusco, Barbera, Cabernet Sauvignon, Pinot were also infected and showed typical symptoms. A few varieties such as Glera and Nebbiolo showed no symptoms or had non-specific symptoms in presence of phytoplasma epidemics since they are tolerant to phytoplasma presence.

- Grapevine yellows symptoms include leaf yellowing or reddening, downward curling very often with a triangle shape of the leaves, shortened internodes, death of tips and shoots, lack of lignification, aborting flowers, shrivelling and early drying of berries. The infected symptomatic cultivars above are from top left: Sangiovese, Lambrusco and Chardonnay.

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Diversity of phytoplasmas detected in Italian vineyards in alternative host species

While the recognition of grapevine yellows symptoms is easily achieved by knowing the typical symptoms, the identification of alternative plant hosts involves molecular testing because in most of the cases these do not show symptoms. Moreover, finding alternative insect vectors includes collection of the insects and molecular identification of phytoplasma presence followed by testing to demonstrate their vector ability. In Italy the TROPICSAFE surveys have allowed detection and identification of diverse phytoplasmas in plants and insects collected inside or in the surroundings of the grapevine infected vineyards.

Among the 300 plant samples belonging to a number of species tested, 16 species were shown to be hosting phytoplasmas. *Parthenocissus quinquefolia* (Vitaceae), *Calystegia sepium* and *Convolvulus* spp. (Convolvulaceae), *Fraxinus excelsior* (Oleaceae), *Quercus* spp. (Fagaceae), *Robinia pseudoacacia* (Fabaceae), *Rosa canina* and *Rubus ulmifolius* (Rosaceae), *Conyza canadensis* and *Tagetes patula* (Asteraceae), and *Skimmia* sp. (Rutaceae) were infected with 'Ca. P. solani' (16SrXII-A phytoplasmas). *Clematis vitalba* (Ranunculaceae), *Sorghum halepense* (Pooideae), *Hedera helix* (Araliaceae), *Rubus* sp. (Rosaceae) and *Morus* spp. (Moraceae) were positive for 'Ca. P. asteris' (16SrI phytoplasmas) presence. In addition, a phytoplasma belonging to the 16SrX group was identified in *Sorghum halepense* and one of the 16SrV group was detected in *Clematis vitalba*; both were however not identified at the 'Ca. Phytoplasma' species level. Only the *P. quinquefolia*, *T. patula* and *Skimmia* sp. plants showed symptoms of leaf reddening and flower virescence suggesting phytoplasma presence.

In Italy the most abundant insect species captured in and around the surveyed vineyards on yellow sticky traps or by sweep netting were *Orientus ishidae*, *Schopoides titanus*, *Hyalesthes obsoletus* and *Hishimonus hamatus*. Other insect species were collected and identified: *Reptalus* spp., *Anaplotettix* spp., *Anaplotettix fuscovenosus*, *Aphorophora alni*, *Centrotus cornutus*, *Neoaliturus fenestratus*, *Philaenus spumarius* and *Jikradia olitoria*. Three leafhopper species, *O. ishidae*, *S. titanus* and *N. fenestratus*, one cixiid, *H. obsoletus*, and *P. spumarius*, tested positive for different phytoplasmas. *O. ishidae* was the most abundant species with 48% of positive samples (69 out of 213 specimens) and had the highest number of infected individuals. The phytoplasma groups and subgroups 16SrI-B, 16SrVI, 16SrVII-A, 16SrX and 16SrX-B were detected for the first time from insects in Italian vineyards. Further phytoplasmas were detected in *Reptalus* spp. (16SrII), *Anaplotettix* spp. (16SrII-D), *A. fuscovenosus* (16SrII, 16SrX-B), *A. alni* (16SrII), *C. cornutus* (16SrII) and *J. olitoria* (16SrXI). Trials to verify their ability to transmit the detected phytoplasmas must be carried out to verify their relevance in the diverse areas infected by grapevine yellows.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Management of alternative grapevine yellows phytoplasma hosts

The epidemiology of grapevine yellows is complex, and the disease management methods include rouging symptomatic grapevines and control of host-plant reservoirs and insect vectors. Alternative plant hosts have an important role as a reservoir from which the insect vectors can transmit the phytoplasmas to grapevines. Phytoplasma insect vectors are primarily leafhoppers, planthoppers and psyllids. The advantage of their identification in a specific agroecosystem is that it allows their environmentally-friendly and targeted removal reducing both the infected material and the labour costs. The biology and epidemiology of the most frequently associated phytoplasmas ('Ca. P. solani', 16SrXII-A and "flavescence dorée", 16SrV-C/-D) are well known; however, climate changes and the recent introduction of alien species of both potential phytoplasma insect vectors and weeds has increased the risk of new phytoplasmas

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or new strains spreading. The TROPICSAFE monitoring identified an increase in the number of plant species infected with 16SrXII-A phytoplasmas as possible source of infection of this phytoplasma in vineyards and in several other agricultural and wild environments. TROPICSAFE also demonstrated that some leafhoppers and planthoppers were infected with grapevine yellows-associated phytoplasmas. Although the presence of the phytoplasmas was confirmed, their presence in an insect is not proof of vector status, which needs to be additionally tested by their experimental transmission to grapevines under controlled conditions.

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Phytoplasma host plants and insect vectors: how to manage them in a sustainable manner?

During TROPICSAFE, the surveys of new alternative host plants of grapevine phytoplasmas, together with possible insect vectors of these phytoplasmas, revealed a long list of different species, especially in Italy. The collected plants in and around vineyards were mostly asymptomatic, representing a hidden reservoir with the potential for further spread of the disease. Therefore, it is recommended to test or preferably remove the most widespread species detected positive for phytoplasma presence near vineyards for prevention of possible infections. It appears clear that only a constant monitoring will allow the prompt detection of phytoplasmas that may infect the studied crops. Appropriate management is linked to the diverse geographical location and agro-ecosystem conditions, but with the appropriate epidemiologic knowledge can be applied as a sustainable tool to reduce economic losses and the environmental pollution.

- Top row from left: symptomatic plants of *P. quinquefolia* and of *T. patula* infected with 'Ca. *P. solani*' (16SrXII-A) in areas in which the vineyards are infected with grapevine yellows in Italy. Bottom a vineyard with symptoms surrounded by diverse weeds and plant species hosting some of the diverse phytoplasmas detected in the TROPICSAFE surveys.

One of the agricultural practices that could be adopted is to use phytoplasma-free grapevine materials when planting new vineyards as demonstrated in the TROPICSAFE project for other insect transmitted prokaryotes such as '*Candidatus Liberibacter*' species in citrus in Cuba. Parallel research carried out by Chilean partners in grapevine in separate projects and in the past by the authors has shown possibilities to produce phytoplasma-free grapevine plants. A sustainable control of infected plants in the fields was demonstrated also by using plasma activated water (PAW) that is however a time consuming and laborious procedure, but produced encouraging results as grapevine berry production and symptom reduction. The use of phytoplasma-free grapevine plants avoids the dissemination of the pathogens in the environment and the acquisition of them from potential insect vectors present in the environment or incidentally introduced, reducing the risk of grapevine yellows epidemic outbreaks without the use of specific insecticides. The use of insecticides, although specific for the insect vectors, is not eliminating the risk of phytoplasma transmission since it is limited by the economic threshold it has biological problems in reaching all the individuals and it is reducing the biodiversity, the resilience and the safety of the vineyard agroecosystems.

- Plasma activated water (PAW) treatments to improve the fitness of plants and induce some resistance reducing the pathogen presence. (A) Micropropagated periwinkle shoots PAW-treated by submersion; (B) grapevine plants cultivar Chardonnay PAW-treated by root drenching; (C) periwinkle plants treated by upside down submersion (Zambon *et al.*, 2020).

KEY WORDS

Grapevine yellows, phytoplasmas, symptomatology, alternative host species, phytoplasma free plant production

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Grapevine yellows threatening the grapevine industry

Grapevine yellows, such as “bois noir”, “flavescence dorée” and aster yellows, are serious diseases of grapevine associated with phytoplasma presence that threaten grapevine production and international trade. These diseases lead to severely reduced yields and infected plants may decline and die. Grapevine production in three grapevine-growing regions of South Africa is threatened by the aster yellows disease that is associated with ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*’ presence (Carstens, 2008; Engelbrecht *et al.*, 2010). Apart from Africa, aster yellows phytoplasma has been reported in grapevine in Europe and North and South America. Worldwide South Africa ranks 9th in the production of wine with some 300,000 people directly or indirectly employed in the industry (SAWIS, 2015; OVI, 2019). Phytoplasmas rely on both their host plant and insect vectors for survival. They can spread in grapevine fields through vegetative propagation of infected plant material and insect vector species (leafhoppers, planthoppers and psyllids). In South Africa, the aster yellows disease is transmitted by the leafhopper *Mgenia fuscovaria* (Krüger *et al.*, 2011). Currently the management of grapevine yellows relies largely on the use of insecticides to control the insect vectors. However, insecticides are not always effective because they may not prevent the pathogen transmission in the short term, their use may not be sustainable due to negative effects on human health and the environment, or their use may not be feasible, for example in organic production systems. Improved knowledge of the aster yellows - plant host - insect vector pathosystem can be used to develop sustainable integrated management methods in addition to the chemical control of the insect vectors.

- Above: map of South African provinces and distribution of the aster yellows phytoplasma in the Western Cape province (red circles). Below: grapevine plant with symptoms of aster yellows disease (A); downward curling of the leaves in a white cultivar (B).

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Integrated management of aster yellows disease in vineyards

TROPICSAFE aims to develop new solutions to manage grapevine yellows, based on improved knowledge of the biology of the associated phytoplasmas and insect vectors, epidemiology, development of reliable, cost-effective detection methods, and exploring crop resistance/tolerance. The results of surveys in South Africa on phytoplasmas in grapevine, alternative host plants and insects have been used to develop new sustainable and eco-friendly management strategies. These include reduction and adaptation of insecticide treatments to local climatic conditions, sanitation, management of reservoir plant species and alternative host plants of insect vectors that contribute to the spread of the diseases, and adaptation of agronomical practices.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

A management plan for aster yellows disease in grapevine in South Africa

A management plan for aster yellows phytoplasma disease in South Africa has been developed for use by managers and growers. This includes early detection of infected plants, planting phytoplasma-free material, recommendations for leafhopper monitoring, management of reservoir plant species, and management of the insect vectors based on research carried out during TROPICSAFE project and previous research findings.

- Sampling of alternative host plants in the Western Cape, South Africa. Measurement of plant size (A), taking a photographic record (B), labelling and sampling the plant (C).

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Specific vineyards management

M. fuscovaria is active all year round. Nymphs and adults have been recorded on grapevine during the growing season and on weeds that might host the aster yellows phytoplasma during the remainder of the year. The recommended strategy is therefore to monitor the leafhopper not only through the growing season, but throughout the year with yellow sticky traps. Management decisions and timing is based on the presence and population size of *M. fuscovaria*, grapevine phenology, and climate. Sanitation measures to prevent the disease spread include the planting of only aster yellows-free material, detection, marking and removal of infected plant material, such as shoots and infected plants. A further important measure is the removal of alternative host plants of aster yellows or of the insect vector. Weed management is essential as weeds from different plant families are infected by aster yellows phytoplasma or, when grapevines are dormant, they are hosts for *M. fuscovaria*. Insecticides for foliar application or soil drenches have been registered for the management of this insect vector. Insecticide applications according to the manufacturer's specifications are based on the presence of the insect vector in high risk areas or on its population size in lower risk areas.

• Monitoring the leafhopper vector *Mgenia fuscovaria* (A) (Michael Stiller) with yellow sticky traps (B).

KEY WORDS

Integrated pest management, sanitation, alternative host plants, phytoplasmas, leafhopper vector

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CITRUS

“HUANGLONGBING”

■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

The importance of citrus in TROPICSAFE partner countries

One aim of TROPICSAFE is the impact evaluation of the solutions proposed to manage citrus “huanglongbing” (HLB), detected in several areas of the world where it has caused big losses. The citrus market analysis is conducted in Cuba, Guadeloupe (France) and Spain, processing official data of FAOSTAT, integrated with information published by the National Statistical Offices or available in literature. In Cuba and Guadeloupe, the effect of HLB have had consequences on the citrus production and commercialization. Spain is not yet affected by the disease, but one of its insect vectors (*Trioza erytreae*) was found in North-Western Spain in 2014, so the risk of infection is very high. In fact, a new Horizon 2020 project, called PRE-HLB, was recently started aiming at developing and implementing a holistic contingency plan to protect Europe’s citrus sector.

Preventing the disease from entering Europe is key to the European citrus market. Economic and social aspects intertwine in this analysis, where the market aspects drop the last piece of the agro-food chain, defining the relative importance of crops at national and international level.

• Romero Barros, Bodegón de naranjas (Córdoba, Museum of fine arts).

■ LATEST RESEARCH RESULTS

Overview on the importance of citrus production

Citrus are the most important fruit tree crops in the world: cultivated in 168 countries on a surface of 12.7 million ha, the production of the sector is about 143 million tons (15.8 t/ha of yield on average) for a gross production value of 66.4 billion US\$ in 2019 (FAOSTAT, 2019). Globally, production and harvested area are increasing (+29% and +13% respectively) in the last 10 years. More than 50% of world citrus production is concentrated in six countries, which leadership is changed in the last ten years: from 2009 to 2019 the production of China increased significantly (+71%), while United States of America have reduced their production (-33%).

According to FAOSTAT (2019), China is the leader, with almost 44 million tons of production representing (22% of the total), followed by Brazil (10%), India (7%), Mexico and United States of America (4%), and Spain (3%).

Except in Europe and Australia, “huanglongbing” has been detected in the most important producing countries, where it is a serious limiting factor for the production and commercialization. Economic losses caused by HLB presence have been estimated in many countries and it represents a serious threat to the market. Several analyses on the importance and impact of the disease on production and market are available in literature (a relative outdated literature is available from South-Eastern Asia, where the disease was observed for the first time).

- Distribution of HLB in the world and main citrus growing countries (CAB International’s Invasive Species Compendium 2019, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations).

■ THE TROPICSAFE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

The citrus market in Cuba, Guadeloupe and Spain

Cuba: According to ONEI, in 2017 citrus crops in Cuba were cultivated on about 19,700 ha with a production of 98,761 tons. This data is very far from the peak of production reached in the ‘90s when the country was among the big producers in the world with about 1 million tons of citrus. After the Soviet bloc collapsed in 1989 and the Cuban citrus industry was reorganized, in 2009 the citrus production saw a downward trend due to HLB presence. Cuba’s fresh fruit exports decreased after 1989 under the competition of Israel and Spain and the citrus industry gave more emphasis to the processed citrus products. The disease was detected in 2006: the average yield of citrus orchards (9.0 t/ha in 2009) decreased until 5 t/ha in 2017 and the amount of citrus produced was subjected to a significant reduction (-76% from 2009 to 2017). The consequence was downsizing the citrus industry and import-export.

Guadeloupe: About 350 ha of the agricultural area are dedicated to citrus cultivation and, although the sector represents about 80% of fruit production, the contribution to French national production is marginal. Even with falls consequent to the hurricanes, the citrus production in Guadeloupe has increased from 1981 until 2011. Then, according to AGRESTE, the overall citrus production has decreased from 5,850 tons in 2011 to 1,542. The reason in the last negative trend is linked to HLB presence, detected in 2012. The importance of citrus in this country is mostly related to internal consumption. In 2016 only 174 tons have been exported while the quantity of import amounted to 6,707 tons. The local government has implemented an action plan to fight against the disease.

Spain: More than 6 million tons of citrus are produced in Spain, leading country in the European citrus market. Around 25% of the total volume goes to the processing industry while 75% is marketed as fresh. More than 210 million euros of turnover have been generated by the orange juice export, mainly to the European Union market (France, Germany, UK, and Portugal).

• Citrus production in Guadeloupe from 1981 to 2017 (AGRESTE).

• Citrus export in Cuba from 1961 to 2019 (tons) (FAOSTAT).

■ SCIENTIFIC DATA AND FIRST RESULTS

Consideration on the socioeconomic impact of “huanglongbing” on citrus agro-food chain

The market analysis and the identification of the most important socioeconomic characteristics of the citrus sector in the selected countries are being developed on two interrelated levels. The first is focused on the quantification of production, import, and export of citrus and citrus products in Cuba, Guadeloupe, and Spain. The second describes the organization of the agro-food chain at the local level, to identify all the subjects involved and the potential impact of the proposed pathogen management strategy. The impact of “huanglongbing” on the agricultural economy of citrus growing countries has provoked in Cuba a decrease in the citrus surface and production, against which the government has replied with a pest management plan and with a new market policy (processing products and introducing a new brand). The general sector organization, the interaction with historical research centres and the market dimension, makes the Cuban citrus agro-food chain open to set up specific innovation-oriented to promptly detect the disease. Guadeloupe has experienced the disease for some years: the citrus sector in this country is mainly organized locally, with an internal market of size not sufficient to reach other countries. However, the detection and control of “huanglongbing” appear crucial to guarantee a minimum revenue to farmers, and the internal supply of products. Spain has the most structured agro-food chain, with a developed market, big production and a developed system of commercialization, especially in the European Union market. “Huanglongbing” has been not detected yet, but an epidemic outbreak of “huanglongbing” could have serious economic consequences.

KEY WORDS

Citrus, market, socioeconomic aspects, “huanglongbing”, disease

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Risk of the spread of the '*Candidatus Liberibacter africanus*'

Very little is known about the alternate host plants and insect vectors of the important pathogen of citrus, '*Candidatus Liberibacter africanus*' which is associated with the citrus greening disease. This is an important knowledge gap, as import of these alternate hosts plants or accidental introduction of an insect vector, could serve as a means of spread of the pathogen to not yet infected parts of the world, including Europe. A survey of a number of samples of potential alternate plant hosts was performed focussing mainly on plants occurring in the Western Cape province of South Africa. It has been shown that tree and shrub specimens of the Rutaceae, indigenous to South Africa, are commonly infected by these bacteria, with each plant genus having a unique subspecies of it. It is important to ascertain if alternate hosts to citrus exist in South Africa. Morphology and barcoding were used to confirm the identity of the plant hosts. The monitoring of psyllid species observed on these plants and the barcoding of all morphogroups observed, as well as attempts at more classical identification by morphology were carried out.

- Top figures: symptoms of citrus greening. Lower left figure: the psyllid vector, *Trioza erythrae*. Lower right figure: pockmarks of *T. erythrae* nymphs on leaves of *Vepris lanceolata*.

■ LATEST RESEARCH RESULTS

Alternate host plants of '*Candidatus Liberibacter africanus*' *sensu lato* in South Africa

Studies to determine whether indigenous members of the Rutaceae (*Calodendrum capense*, *Clausena anisata*, *Oricia* spp., *Teclea* spp., *Vepris* spp. and *Zanthoxylum* spp.) serve as reservoirs for '*Ca. L. africanus*', associated to the citrus greening disease in commercial citrus orchards are in progress. Each indigenous plant genus contained a unique lineage of '*Ca. L. africanus*' (Roberts *et al.*, 2015). A relatively large percentage of the samples collected of each plant genus was positive for presence of the pathogen, suggesting the common and widespread occurrence of this bacterium in South Africa. These studies were expanded to include the relatively large group of Western Cape fynbos members of the Rutaceae, but not to non Rutaceae hosts. The genus-wide '*Ca. Liberibacter*' PCR assay (Roberts *et al.*, 2015) was used for these studies. The psyllid *Trioza erythrae* is known as a vector of '*Ca. L. africanus*' and the *Diaphorina citri*, can also transmit this bacterium experimentally. The insect vectors of the diverse '*Ca. L. africanus*' strains detected are still unknown.

Vepris lanceolata

Calodendrum capense

Zanthoxylum capense

Teclea spp

Oricia bachmannii

Clausena anisata

- Rutaceous species hosts of '*Candidatus Liberibacter africanus*' *sensu lato* identified in South Africa.

■ THE TROPICSAFE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

Survey for identification of alternate host plants of '*Candidatus Liberibacter africanus*' sensu lato

Under the framework of TROPICSAFE, a survey and characterization of '*Ca. L. africanus*' subspecies, and their potential insect vectors in alternative host plants to citrus, was conducted. Weed and indigenous plant samples were collected at several localities in the Western Cape, South Africa during different seasons in 2017 and 2018, often around citrus orchards or vineyards. The leaf material collected was stored at -80°C until DNA extractions could be performed. Quantitative PCR tests specific for '*Ca. Liberibacter*' detection were conducted. PCR was also conducted on samples positive by qPCR, and the amplicons obtained were sequenced. The barcoding of alternative host plants was performed for their taxonomic identification.

The same areas were also surveyed for the presence of potential insect vectors (psyllids) prior to sampling them for the tests to detect the bacteria. This was done by vacuum sampling (DVAC machine) the insects and storing them in absolute ethanol for subsequent species identification and molecular analysis. Gross insect identification was made by studying morphological characters and relevant insects were subjected to DNA extraction using a non-destructive TNES buffer-based extraction method that maintain the insects intact for a following identification and for deposition of voucher specimens in museums.

- Using a suction device to collect insects from fynbos plants in South Africa.

■ SCIENTIFIC DATA AND FIRST RESULTS

Identification of alternate host plants for 'Candidatus Liberibacter africanus' and its subspecies

Three field trips were conducted, in September 2017, January and August, 2018. The first two were to the Worcester/Robertson/Slanghoek areas of the Breederiver valley, Western Cape, while the last one was to the Vredendal/Lutzville, on the Cape west coast. Twelve collection sites were utilised, of which two were in the vicinity of citrus orchards. Using the DVAC device, insects were collected from 1,001 plant samples. Leaf and twig materials of each of these plants were also collected. DNA was extracted from all plant samples. Between 5 and 100 specimens of each of 42 species of plants were collected (with a maximum of 20 samples of a specific species per site). These plants were identified by morphological characters and amplifying the *rbcl* gene of representative plant samples. All samples were tested for 'Ca. Liberibacter' spp. presence by qPCR. Samples with Ct values lower than 30 (143) were also tested for 'Ca. Liberibacter' presence by PCR targeting the *rplJ* and the *omp* genes. Seventy-eight of the samples with Ct values less than 30 were from one of the three *Atriplex* species collected, while 14 were from *Lycium* species, 15 from *Rapistrum rugosum*, while fewer samples were from a number of other species. None of the samples yielded amplicons in PCR. No psyllids were observed amongst numerous other insects collected from these samples. One sample of *Atriplex*, positive in qPCR was submitted to next-generation sequencing.

- Stands of *Atriplex lindleyi*, a plant species with a large number of samples yielding low Ct values for 'Candidatus Liberibacter' detection by specific qPCR tests.

KEY WORDS

'Candidatus Liberibacter africanus', citrus greening, alternate hosts, *Trioza erytreae*

FURTHER INFORMATION

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

“Huanglongbing”: a lethal disease of citrus

Citrus is the most important fruit tree crop in the world, with an annual production estimated in 143 million tons (FAOSTAT, 2019). “Huanglongbing” (HLB) is considered the most destructive disease of commercial citrus species worldwide. It affects all citrus varieties, severely reducing the yield and the performance of the crops. The disease is associated with the presence of ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter*’ species and it is transmitted by the psyllids *Diaphorina citri* and *Trioza erytrae*. To date, HLB is present in every continent except Australia and mainland Europe, although one of its insect vectors was detected in the Iberian Peninsula in 2014 (Cocuzza *et al.*, 2017). Its impact is very high in the Americas and Africa. For example, in Florida, HLB caused losses of 4,554 million US dollars in six years (2005-2011) (Hodges and Spreen, 2012). Since there is no effective control except to prevent trees from becoming infected, awareness of the disease and rapid identification of its symptoms are essential. However, there is still a clear lack of information about “huanglongbing”, especially in those countries that are still free of the disease.

• Infected citrus plots in Guadeloupe: A, mandarins; B, oranges; C, lime.

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Insect vectors and symptoms of the HLB disease

The ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter*’ responsible of citrus “huanglongbing” disease slow the plant growth, reduce flowering and generate losses of production in quantity and quality, before eventually the tree dies (Fujikawa *et al.*, 2013). Two species of citrus psyllids can transmit this bacterium: *Diaphorina citri* (Asian citrus psyllid) and *Trioza erytrae* (African citrus psyllid). The inoculation period is about one hour and the symptoms appear about four months after the infection (Batool *et al.*, 2007). *D. citri* is present in most tropical regions in Asia and America and also in all the citrus producing areas in the Caribbean. This psyllid is the most dangerous and widespread species in the world. *T. erytrae* is present in Africa, the Canary Islands, Madeira and recently in north of Spain and Portugal. There is a major concern that the arrival of these psyllids would have a disastrous effect in Europe (ANSES, 2019). The first step for disease prevention is to detect the disease and its insect vectors presence. It is necessary to detect as early as possible the presence of the vectors and the disease in citrus orchards and in private gardens, in order to establish

the appropriate HLB management practices. Protocols for monitoring the vectors and detecting the disease are part of the TROPICSAFE project. It was found that very small quantities of psyllids are sufficient to infect orchards, with sometimes non-symptomatic trees that can die off very quickly.

• Nymph (A) and adult (B) of *Diaphorina citri* (CIRAD), instars of *D. citri* (C). Nymph (D) and adult (E) of *Trioza erytreae*, instars of *T. erytreae* (F) (A. Tena, IVIA).

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

How to detect insect vectors and HLB in the field

Both insect vectors are identifiable at both nymph and adult stages by visual and/or microscopic observations.

Symptoms of HLB are characteristic and can be easily recognized in the field: asymmetric yellow blotch of leaves and desiccation, premature fall, deformation of fruits. Leaves may also become thicker, leathery, the midribs and the lateral veins are sometimes enlarged, swollen and corky (Batool *et al.*, 2007). However, some trees can stay asymptomatic at the beginning of the disease, therefore, a molecular detection of 'Ca. Liberibacter' is necessary.

Different DNA amplification methods, including polymerase chain reaction (PCR), quantitative PCR, nested PCR, and loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP), can be used to detect HLB in the plant samples (Iftikhar *et al.*, 2016). However, these laboratory-based detection methods are often time-consuming and expensive. TROPICSAFE project is now developing more practical and accessible detection techniques that could be performed in the field.

• Major symptoms of HLB on citrus plants, leaves and fruits (ASSOFWI).

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Detection of the HLB in a small scale survey in the project countries

Symptomatic citrus samples were collected in Cuba, Jamaica, and Guadeloupe. DNA extraction was performed from 1 g of leaf midribs. PCR amplification for ‘*Ca. Liberibacter*’ species was performed with primers OA1/OI2 and OI1/OI2c (Jagoueix *et al.*, 1996), the sequencing confirmed the presence of ‘*Ca. L. asiaticus*’ in the majority of the tested samples. The presence of the pathogen resulted not related to the tree variety or to the geographic locations.

Sample	Location	HLB positive/total tested
Cuba		
Persian lime	Ceballos/Ciego de Avila	21/21
Orange Valencia		30/30
Tangerine		1/1
Grapefruit		12/12
Persian lime	Sola/Camagüey	12/12
Orange Valencia		2/2
Grapefruit		2/2
Persian lime	Jagüey/Matanzas	15/16
Orange		29/30
Tangerine		2/2
Grapefruit		2/2
Lemon		3/3
Orange	Arimao/Cienfuegos	2/2
Grapefruit		6/6
Mexican lime	La Habana	0/1

Sample	Location	HLB positive/total tested	
Guadeloupe			
Orange Valencia Rod Red	Trois-Rivières	0/1	
Orange Navelina		0/1	
Mandarine Creole		1/1	
Tahiti lime		4/4	
Mexican lime	Nord Vieux-Habitants	1/1	
Tahiti lime		1/1	
Tangelo Nova	Vieux-Habitants	0/1	
Tangelo Jackson		1/2	
Orange Navel		1/1	
Mandarine Tample		2/2	
Orange Valencia Late		1/2	
Orange Maltaise		0/1	
Mandarine Falglo		1/1	
Tangelo Triumph		1/1	
Tangor Ellendale		1/1	
Orange Navelate		1/1	
Orange Fisher Navel		1/2	
Flhor AG1 4X		CIRAD Capesterre	0/2
Jamaica			
Citrus company		Bay Brook	4/5
Citrus Montego Bay	Montego Bay	1/1	

- Results of the survey for the detection of '*Candidatus Liberibacter*' in citrus species in Cuba, Guadeloupe and Jamaica (Bertaccini *et al.*, 2019).

KEY WORDS

Detection, symptomatology, citrus, disease, insect vectors

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INTRODUCTION OF THE MAIN PARASITOID OF *TRIOZA ERYTREA* IN EUROPE

An option for the biological control of the “huanglongbing” disease

■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

“Huanglongbing”: a threat to the citrus industry in Europe

The African citrus psyllid, *Trioza erytreae* (Del Guercio) (Hemiptera: Triozidae), is the most recent citrus pest introduced to the European mainland. It was detected in north-western Spain in 2014 (Cocuzza *et al.*, 2017), and since then it has spread along the Portuguese coast as far as Lisbon, infesting citrus trees in private gardens. This psyllid transmits the citrus greening or “huanglongbing” (HLB) disease, which is one of the most devastating citrus diseases in the world (Bové 2006). This disease is associated with three phloem α -proteobacteria: ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus*’, ‘*Ca. L. americanus*’ and ‘*Ca. L. africanus*’. *Trioza erytreae* is a vector of ‘*Ca. L. africanus*’.

Although HLB has not been detected in mainland Europe (Cocuzza *et al.*, 2017), the mere presence of the psyllid is a major threat for the Mediterranean citrus industry. As an example of the economic impact of HLB, this disease caused losses of 4,554 million US dollars and more than 8,000 jobs directly or indirectly linked to the Florida citrus industry between 2005 and 2011 in the USA (Hodges and Spreen, 2012).

• Asymptomatic (left) and symptomatic (centre and right) citrus trees infected by “huanglongbing” or greening. The disease is transmitted by the psyllids *Trioza erytreae* and *Diaphorina citri*. Photo by César Monzó.

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

A natural enemy to control the disease

One of the main aims of TROPICSAFE is to develop advanced and novel pest management strategies that provide a reduction in the environmental impact of plant protection approaches. Among these strategies, the classical biological control (*i.e.* the introduction of natural enemies from the area of origin of the target pest) is probably the most feasible and environmentally friendly strategy to manage *T. erytreae* in Europe (Cocuzza *et al.*, 2017).

TROPICSAFE has initiated a classical biological control program to introduce the parasitoid *Tamarixia dryi* (= *Tetrastichus dryi*) (Waterston) (Hymenoptera, Eulophidae) from its area of origin (South Africa). This parasitoid is the most abundant and effective biological control agent of *T. erytreae* in sub-Saharan Africa. This solitary ectoparasitoid has already been successfully introduced to Reunion Island and Mauritius in the 1980s, where *T. dryi* regulated the populations of the psyllid (Aubert and Quilici, 1986).

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Collection and importation of the parasitoid

Taking into consideration the success of *T. dryi*, the Valencian Institute of Agrarian Research (IVIA) applied to obtain the legal permits to introduce this parasitoid into Europe. Once obtained, four citrus producing areas of South Africa (Western Cape, Mpumalanga, Limpopo and Gauteng) were sampled from September 21st to December 9th of 2017 with the collaboration of the Universities of Pretoria and Stellenbosch and the Citrus Research International (CRI) to obtain and establish several isolines of *T. dryi*. The parasitoid was identified by a combination of morphological and molecular characterization. During the survey, two other species of primary parasitoids were recovered, including a new species of the genus *Tamarixia* that is under description by specialists at the University of Riverside (California, USA).

On December 2017, *T. dryi* isolines were sent to the Canarian Institut of Agrarian Research where a colony of the parasitoid was established. During 2018, several laboratory studies were conducted to: i) confirm that the imported parasitoids are not infested by '*Ca. L. africanus*'; ii) determine the specificity of *T. dryi*; and iii) study its potential as a biological control agent. These studies are all required before it is released into the field.

- Collection of *Tamarixia dryi* in four citrus producing areas from South Africa in 2017. Details of the colony of *T. dryi* established under controlled conditions in Spain before it is released.

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

A high potential to control *Trioza erytreae* in Europe

Laboratory experiments have demonstrated that *T. dryi* is a highly specific parasitoid and its release and establishment in Europe within a classical biological control program of *T. erytreae* should not affect native psyllid species. *T. dryi* did not parasitize any of the 11 non-target psyllids tested, including five species of the genus *Trioza*. These psyllids were selected and tested for their phylogenetic proximity to *T. erytreae* as well as for ecological reasons.

Molecular techniques confirmed that the specimens of *T. dryi* were not infected by '*Ca. L. africanus*'. Therefore, and taking into consideration the two latter results, no significant environmental impact is expected with the release of *T. dryi*.

Laboratory and field assays have also demonstrated that *T. dryi* has a high potential to control *T. erytreae* in Europe. Female parasitoids attack and parasitize *T. erytreae* nymphs from the 3rd to the 5th instar. The parasitoid can survive for more than 30 days when it feeds on the honeydew of its hosts. Its sex ratio in the colonies and field tends to be female biased (more females than males are produced). It tends to feed on hosts of different sizes. These characteristics highlight the potential of *T. dryi* for biological control of *T. erytreae*.

- Details of the parasitoid *Tamarixia dryi* when it attacks and parasitizes the psyllid *Trioza erytrae*, egg (red arrow), pupae (below *Trioza erytrae*) and adult of *T. dryi*; colony of *T. erytrae* parasitized by *T. dryi*.

KEYWORDS

Citrus, integrated pest management (IPM), biological control, parasitism

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

The main threat to citrus industry has no biological control agents in Europe

The citrus greening or “huanglongbing” disease is one of the most devastating citrus diseases in the world (Bové, 2006). This disease is associated with three phloem α -proteobacteria: ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus*’, ‘*Ca. L. americanus*’ and ‘*Ca. L. africanus*’. The disease is transmitted by the African citrus psyllid *Trioza erytreae* (Del Guercio) (Hemiptera: Triozidae) and the Asian citrus psyllid *Diaphorina citri* Kuwayama (Hemiptera: Liviidae). None of these insect vectors was present in mainland Europe until 2014, when *T. erytreae* was detected in north-western Spain (Cocuzza et al., 2017). Since then, the psyllid has spread towards the southwest of the Portuguese coast reaching Lisbon province (DGAV, 2019). Although the psyllid has not reached the main citrus-producing areas and the pathogen has not been detected (Siverio et al., 2017), the spread of *T. erytreae* in mainland Europe has alarmed citrus growers from the Mediterranean countries. Recent studies carried out by TROPICSAFE and other research groups have demonstrated that the psyllid vector has no potential biological control agents that can control it in Europe.

- Left: citrus flush infested by *Trioza erytreae* with open gall-like structures produced by *T. erytreae* nymphs. Right: different stages of *T. erytreae*: eggs, nymphs and adults recently emerged.

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

A parasitic wasp to prevent “huanglongbing” in Europe

One of the main aims of TROPICSAFE is to develop advanced and novel pest management strategies that provide a reduction in the environmental impact of plant protection approaches. TROPICSAFE has initiated a classical biological control program to introduce the parasitoid *Tamarixia dryi* (= *Tetrastichus dryi*) (Waterston) (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) from South Africa. This parasitoid is the most abundant and effective biological control agent of *T. erytreae* in Africa. The parasitoid was introduced in the Canary Islands, an archipelago in the Atlantic Ocean belonging to Spain. After rearing it and testing its specificity in collaboration with the Canarian Institute of Agricultural Research (ICIA) (Pérez-Rodríguez et al. 2019; Urbaneja-Bernat et al., 2019), it was released in the spring of 2018 in the Canary Islands and in fall of 2019 in the northwest of Iberian Peninsula (Galicia, mainland Spain).

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Release of *Tamarixia dryi* in the field

Taking into consideration the success of *T. dryi* in other areas, and the results obtained under laboratory conditions, TROPICSAFE together with ICIA and the “Servicio de Sanidad Vegetal de Canarias” reared, released and monitored the parasitoid *T. dryi* in the field. The parasitoid was released in the spring of 2018 in a citrus orchard that belongs to ICIA and is located in La Laguna, northeast of Tenerife.

After its release, the spread of *T. dryi* was measured during the fall and winter of 2018 and 2019. For this, citrus trees from different localities throughout the Tenerife Island (60 × 40 km) were sampled to determine the presence of the parasitoid; the parasitism rates of *T. dryi* were also measured in two citrus orchards in 2019. For this, shoots infested with *T. dryi* were collected and transported to the laboratory. Once there, the number of alive and parasitized psyllid nymphs were counted under a binocular microscope to determine the potential of the parasitoid in field.

The same procedure was followed in mainland Spain (Pontevedra, Galicia) where *T. dryi* was released in three localities in the fall of 2019 and the spring of 2020. The spread of *T. dryi* was measured during the summer of 2020 and 2021 with the collaboration of the “Servicio de Sanidad Vegetal de Galicia” and the public companies TRAGSA and TRAGSATEC.

- The parasitoid *Tamarixia dryi* parasitizing the psyllid *Trioza erytreae* in the laboratory (left). A detail of the release of *T. dryi* in the field, the parasitoids are leaving the tube where they were transported (right).

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Tamarixia dryi controls *Trioza erytreae* in the Canary Islands

The field data demonstrates that *T. dryi* spread rapidly throughout the Tenerife Island. After its release in the northeast of the island in spring of 2018, the parasitoid was detected in the west and south of Tenerife (50 km from the release point) in the fall of 2018. Moreover, the parasitoid was recovered in 80% of the 83 locations sampled in the fall and winter of 2018 and 2019. Taking into consideration the different climates of the north (humid) and south (dry) parts of the island, its rapid spread suggests that *T. dryi* will be able to establish and spread once it is released in the Iberian Peninsula.

The dynamics of *T. erytreae* and the parasitism rates by *T. dryi* were measured in two citrus orchards that had high levels of the psyllid in previous years. The levels of *T. erytreae* were extremely low in 2019, likely by the introduction of the parasitoid *T. dryi*. In the two citrus orchards sampled in 2019, parasitism rates reached almost 90% and the

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populations of the psyllid did not recover after summer, even when new flush was available. These results demonstrate the efficacy of *T. dryi* as biological control agent of *T. erytreae* in the field in Tenerife.

- Seasonal trend of *Trioza erytreae* and parasitism rate by its parasitoid *Tamarixia dryi* in the Canary Islands in 2019.

Tamarixia dryi controls *Trioza erytreae* in mainland Spain

The field data demonstrates that *T. dryi* spread throughout Pontevedra (Galicia) between the summer of 2020 and 2021. After its release in three localities from Pontevedra, the parasitoid spread up to 2 km from the releasing point in 2020 and more than 40 km in the summer of 2021. Therefore, *T. dryi* has been also able to establish and spread in the Iberian Peninsula.

In the summer of 2020, the percentage of parasitism in the citrus shoots from spring was $38.9 \pm 3.2\%$ in Romai (Portas), $25.7 \pm 3\%$ in O Grove and $7.6 \pm 2.3\%$ in O Rosal. In O Grove, it was also possible to calculate the level of parasitism in the citrus shoots from summer. The percentage of parasitism reached $75.2 \pm 3.6\%$. All the parasitized nymphs of *T. erytreae* were parasitized by *T. dryi* and hyperparasitoids were not recovered.

In the summer of 2021, the density of *T. erytreae* decreased dramatically, likely due to the presence of the *T. dryi*, and it was not possible to calculate the percentage of parasitism. After this success, the parasitoid has been released in all the areas infested by *T. erytreae* in mainland Spain and Portugal.

- A colony of nymphs of *Trioza erytreae* parasitized by the parasitoid *Tamarixia dryi* in Galicia in summer 2020.

KEY WORDS

Citrus, integrated pest management (IPM), classical biological control, *Tamarixia dryi*, *Trioza erytreae*

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THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Sustainable “huanglongbing” management for the citrus industry in Cuba

“Huanglongbing” was discovered in Cuba in late 2006 (Luis *et al.*, 2009), where the citrus production decreased from 500,000 tonnes in 2004 to 100,000 tonnes in 2017. There has been a marked acceleration in decline of the total area planted to citrus since that time, and 20,465 ha have been replanted with alternative crops. A significant reduction in citrus consumer preference has occurred amongst Cuban people. National juice production for exportation has suffered a similar decline. Because no curative methods of HLB are available, a management of the disease is the main alternative to achieve sustainability of the Cuban citrus industry (Batista *et al.*, 2017).

- Geographic locations of citrus enterprises (citrus fruit icon) in provinces (color zones) of Cuba. Citrus areas planted in each one and data of general citrus production in 2017.

- Orchard of the sweet orange Valencia 121 from Ceballos showing a low incidence of HLB-symptomatic plants and a high fruit production (photo by D. Lopez).

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Alternative strategies for biological control of the disease in Cuba

One of the main aims of the TROPICSAFE project is to develop advanced pest integrated management strategies through the reduction of the environmental impact of plant protection strategies. Among these strategies, biological control such as the use of natural products is one of the most feasible and environmentally friendly strategies to manage many insect vectors.

Therefore, the research aims are:

1-to evaluate the efficacy of infected-tree eradication to reduce temporal progress of the disease and to diminish the need for chemical applications;

2-to evaluate two management practices for control of *Diaphorina citri*, the entomopathogenic fungus *Hirsutella* sp. and kaolin applications.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Systematic surveys, application of treatments and observation

The efficacy of eradication on HLB management has been evaluated by comparison of the temporal progress of the disease in two areas in which different strategies are being applied. Six orchards of two citrus enterprises of Cuba were selected: Ceballos in Ciego de Ávila province and Victoria de Girón in Matanzas province. The TROPICSAFE activity has been developed in a block of 900 plants in each orchard. In Ceballos, the strategy includes the use of disease-free trees for replanting, the grove-wide chemical control of the insect vectors (only in the presence of the vector) and when plants are pre-sprouted (to protect new leaves); and removal of infected trees (eradication). In Victoria de Girón, the strategy is similar but without eradication.

The commercial varieties include the sweet orange Valencia [*Citrus sinensis* (L.) Osb.], grapefruit "Marsh" and "Ruby" (*Citrus paradisi* Macf.) grafted, and the rootstocks sour orange (*C. aurantium* L.), "Citranges carrizo" and "C-35" (*Poncirus trifoliata* x *Citrus sinensis*). Since March 2017, systematic surveys every two months have been carried out in each orchard for monitoring symptomatic plants. The main symptom used for visual diagnosis was foliar blotchy mottle.

The entomopathogenic fungus *Hirsutella* was applied in all the citrus enterprises in Cuba. Different isolates were grown from infected adults of *D. citri*. The artificial medium used was Potato Dextrose Agar and the fungus was identified by classical taxonomy based on morphology. Three treatments were applied and compared: (i) *Hirsutella* sp., (ii) systemic and contact insecticides and (iii) untreated (control). The presence of infected nymphs was determined by visual sampling of 20 leaves per plant.

Finally, with regard to the evaluation of efficacy of kaolin 5% application against *D. citri*, the comparison was between the insect presence on plants treated with this product and plants without treatment. The orchard selected ("Valencia" sweet orange) is from the citrus enterprise in the special municipality Isla de la Juventud. The applications of kaolin were in March, May and September 2018. The count of eggs, nymphs and adults of *D. citri* were recorded from March to November 2018. Four flushes/plant were selected according to the cardinal points. An arbitrary scale was used for the *D. citri* population: weak (w): 1- 2 individuals, medium (m): 3-5 and strong (s): more than 5.

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■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

The eradication of diseased plants considerably reduces the incidence of the disease

The eradication results in Ceballos orchards obtained up to November 2019 showed that there was a low incidence of symptomatic plants. In January 2019, a few trees with symptoms were detected located near the roads. This result is mainly related to the efficient control of the insect vector (low population levels) avoiding secondary infections and the extensive spread of the infection. Furthermore, these orchards are far from the oldest. This allowed less frequent applications of chemicals in a preventive manner only at the boundaries of the field. This result is indicating the effectiveness of the tested management strategy. In the orchards of Victoria de Girón, the incidence of the disease was higher than in those of Ceballos. Symptomatic plants were detected since March 2018 and ranged between 13 and 18% at the end of 2019. This is possibly a consequence of the permanence of the source of primary inoculums from non-eradicated infected plants.

The results demonstrate that the elimination of symptomatic trees at a regional scale should be implemented to manage HLB in commercial citrus orchards in Cuba, as it had been previously recommended in other areas (Gottwald, 2010). After two years, the percentage of trees with symptoms was 20% lower in the area where symptomatic trees were eliminated.

• Incidence of “huanglongbing” in citrus orchards without (A) and with (B) eradication programs in Cuba from May 2017 to November 2019.

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Regarding the entomopathogenic fungus practice developed in the citrus enterprises, adults of parasitized *D. citri* were collected in orchards located in Jiguani, Contramaestre and Sola from Granma, Santiago de Cuba and Camaguey provinces. The isolates obtained from these sampled insects included species of the genus *Hirsutella*. The isolates were maintained on PDA medium under controlled conditions. The preliminary results suggest the potential use of this fungus for the biological control of the vector. Comparison of the efficacy of three treatments including (i) *Hirsutella* sp., (ii) systemic and contact insecticides and (iii) untreated (control) is under evaluation.

Some preliminary results for kaolin application showed its repellent capacity since it modified the behavior of *D. citri* and no individuals were detected after the applications. Any *D. citri* population was identified in the first months of the applications (March and May 2018). Only one plant with adults was detected in June and November 2018.

Potential HLB dispersion pathways include the presence of internal inoculum in the orchards (*i.e.* infectious symptomatic plants) and populations of the insect vector. The measures for control are mainly focused on inoculum reduction by frequent removal of HLB-affected trees and control of psyllid vector populations by alternative treatments. These first results indicate that all the tested measures have had a positive effect, both by decreasing the spread of the disease and by decreasing the population levels of the insect vector.

• *D. citri* parasitized by entomopathogenic fungus on citrus leaf (photos by J.L. Rodriguez Tapia).

• Isolate of entomopathogenic fungus on potato dextrose agar medium (photos by M. Ramos).

KEY WORDS

Citrus, integrated pest management (IPM), biological control

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■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Restarting a sustainable citrus fruit production sector in Guadeloupe under high disease pressure

The Asian psyllid vector of '*Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus*' was identified in Guadeloupe in 1998 (Etienne *et al.*, 1998) and citrus "huanglongbing" disease was detected in 2012. As described in other countries, the disease has very bad impacts on citrus fruit production (Gottwald *et al.*, 2007) that decreased from around 6,000 tons in 2005 to just over 1,000 tons in 2017. A regional epidemio-surveillance network was set up by the authorities (DAAF-FREDON) as soon as the disease was discovered to monitor the presence of the insect vector and the disease symptoms. In total, more than 60% of the plots were found infected. A map of the most contaminated areas has also been set up. As there is no curative solution, different sustainable plot management methods have been tested to propose cropping systems to manage the producers' constraints.

Of the 438 analyses carried out from 2012, 264 resulted positive with about 60% of the trees tested infected. Plots detected negative before 2019 are not re-tested annually and can potentially be infected today and thus constitute new sources of infection for the disease (ANSES, 2019). Also in some plots, very few psyllids are observed, but the disease is present. Many countries opt for the destruction of contaminated plants in the field (Lopes *et al.*, 2010) but due to the high cost of plants in Guadeloupe (between 15 and 25 euro/plant), this solution is not applicable, therefore, it seems essential to find a way to live with the disease.

- On the left, citrus fruit production in Guadeloupe (DAAF) and on the right, the map of the plots positive to "huanglongbing" between 2012 and 2018 (FREDON).

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Development of agro-ecological and organic technical processes

The health context related to "huanglongbing" is very complicated in Guadeloupe with very low sanitation level, or destruction of infested plots/infected trees. Only one species tolerant to the disease remains cultivated, the triploid Tahiti lime. The other species, such as oranges, mandarins, and grapefruits, are only produced in very small quantities. Therefore the development of innovative and/or low-input technical routes more resilient to the disease is necessary. It seems essential to break with the old production system that has become inefficient and unsustainable under the constraint of this disease. Two types of cropping systems are therefore tested in an agro-ecological system that saves phytosanitary inputs (IPM) and in an organic system without phytosanitary treatments (BIO).

Trees infected by “huanglongbing” are more susceptible to biotic and abiotic stresses. The objective is to make these systems as efficient as possible to limit these stresses and put the trees in the best possible production conditions. The plots were planted in 2015 at Capesterre Belle Eau and Vieux Habitants to verify the combined effect of cultivation practices and plant material on trees in two different soil and climate contexts, one dry and hot, the other rather hot and humid.

- On the left, mean rainfall map (Météo France) and on the right, soil map (INRA).

- Pictures of the plots PA IPM (left) and PA BIO (right).

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Comparison between agro-ecological and organic management

There is no visible effect of practices on disease control, but there are visible effects on the tree health. The species chosen for this experiment are diploid mandarins and tangelos, coupled with three different grafting stocks, including two tetraploid rootstock. Symptoms, pathogen presence, and tree mortality were assessed since 2015. A high level of technical expertise is required to improve irrigation practices and propose appropriate fertilization protocols that do not induce other stress except the one induced by the disease. It is also important to perform interventions according to the different stages of the trees during the year. It seems essential to determine the level of infection and vector infestation of the plots, before assessing the impact of the cropping systems on the trees. The disease was detected very quickly on the plots and the contamination rates are very high 4 years after planting. The high percentages of disease presence are also influenced by the favorable context on these plots for the insect vector: low altitude, presence of citrus fruits nearby (producers and/or individuals). The BIO plot managed organically by preservation was slightly less infected than the IPM plot. Psyllid larvae parasitized by *Tamarixia radiata* are regularly observed together with a lot of crops auxiliaries in general (chrysopes, beetles...). The plot is biologically controlled. The IPM system should allow a better tree growth.

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Annual growth monitoring was carried out on the plots by measuring the circumference of the trunks at the level of the rootstock (10 cm from the ground) and the variety (5 cm above the graft). This criterion was selected to determine the impact of the technical management implemented (IPM or BIO) on tree growth. This indicator will also allow selecting the most efficient rootstocks and varieties adapted to the soil and the climate. The trees on the IPM plot were growing faster. The IPM technical path implemented seems to allow faster tree growth than the BIO technical path.

- It should be noted that the BIO plot suffered numerous damages due to breakage and cutbacks in the irrigation network. The plot remained without water for several months, and this was strongly affecting the trees.
- The trees on the IPM plot were not pruned to limit stress while those BIO were pruned annually since planting. A severe shape pruning was achieved in the first year of planting, delaying the growth. The tetraploid rootstock (Citrumelo 4x) had a dwarfing effect compared to diploid (Citrumelo 2x) on both plots. The study of fruit yields and quality is ongoing as production (first fruit in 2017) begins to become homogeneous in 2019. The IPM plot seems better than BIO plot.

	BIO	IPM
Plantation year	2015	2015
First symptoms	End of 2016	2016
First 'Ca. L. asiaticus' detection	2017	2016
Mortality rate of the trees in 2019	30%	0,5%
Contamination rate in 2019	89%	100%

- Evolution of the sanitary status of the plots between 2015 and 2019.

- Annual growth monitoring on the plots.

		Fertilisation	Irrigation	Weed management	Pest management
BIO	Type	Organic + Foliar	Aspersions	Mechanical	Biological control
	Products	Italpolina Guanito, Phénix + sheep manure + Myr Micro, Auxym, Trainer	Micro aspersions	Scraper on the row / Gyro crusher in the inter-row	Black soap+ Vermicompost juice + effective microorganisms created produced according to a technology developed by EEPFIH at Perico - Matanzas- Cuba.
	Frequency	Monthly	Daily	Monthly	Occasional
IPM	Type	Mineral (NPK)+ Foliar	Aspersions	Mechanical	Integrated pest management
	Products	Urea, DAP, 11-11-33, 12-6-20 + Hortal, Mérol	Micro aspersions	Scraper on the row / Mower in the inter-row area	Vertimec + Karate + Oviphyt/black soap with foliar fertiliser
	Frequency	Monthly	Daily	Monthly	Bimonthly

- Practices implemented on the plots.

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Proposal of a standard IPM technical itinerary

It is known that under “huanglongbing” presence, various biotic and abiotic stresses can limit the production and even contribute to tree death. The IPM itinerary seems, therefore, the more appropriate management method. A typical IPM system is presented below. The successions and combinations of farming operations are set up to produce minimizing the tree stresses. In the context of integrated production, each operation identified in the scheme is important and should not be neglected, to maintain the orchard in good shape. The IPM system had better results in the study carried out, however, it should be noted that, given the difficulties encountered in maintaining the BIO plot (water stress in particular), the results obtained are probably lower than those that would have been obtained for a system as rigorous as the IPM, but which would only use organic inputs with regular irrigation. Also, biological cultural innovations will be implemented and deserve to be validated for organic production by exclusively organic fertilization with the use of efficient micro-organisms, composts, manure regularly brought in, production of bio-organic pits at tree planting, biological intensification of the system with the addition of aromatic and/or repellent companion plants, redesign of systems by integrating other crops with economic potential to compensate the losses linked to the disease (fruit trees, banana, coffee, cocoa). A new plot was planted in November 2019 and results will be presented together with those of the BIO cropping system.

• IPM cropping system proposed in Guadeloupe.

KEY WORDS

Citrus fruits, “huanglongbing”, integrated pest management, agro-ecology, organic farming, cropping system

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USE OF NEXT GENERATION SEQUENCING FOR CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROBIOMES FROM PHYTOPLASMA / "HUANGLONGBING" INFECTED PLANTS

Bacterial microbiomes in plant and insect materials infected by '*Candidatus Liberibacter*' and '*Candidatus Phytoplasma*' species

■ THE PROBLEM ADDRESSED

Verifying the bacterial populations

Plants are inhabited by a wide diversity of both beneficial and harmful microorganisms such as fungi, bacteria and viruses. These microorganisms, the microbiome, closely interact in networks that can for instance be antagonistic or symbiotic. '*Candidatus Phytoplasmas*' and '*Ca. Liberibacter*' species are part of this network and compete with the remaining microbiome for nutrients and space interacting with other plant-associated microorganisms. This interaction could play important roles for the success of infections and for the ability to spread from plant to plant by insect vectors. Furthermore, the genetic variability of these bacteria, which is often overseen by current methods, could be important for pathogen survival, development of symptoms and transmission by insect vectors. A large number of samples from diverse geographical location, diverse plant and insect species and infected by these pathogenic bacterias confirmed by nested-PCR testing were used for the microbiome determination.

Host species	Country of origin	Partner	Number of samples
Citrus	Guadeloupe	ASSO	15
Citrus	Jamaica	CIB	5
Citrus	Mexico	COLPO	9
Citrus	Cuba	IIFT	24
Citrus	South Africa	PTHSL	8
Insects	Mexico	COLPO	46
Insects	Cuba	IIFT	30
Coconut palm	Jamaica	CIB	19
Coconut palm	Mexico	CICY	14
Coconut palm	Mexico	COLPO	12
Coconut palm	Ghana	CSIR	49
Coconut palm	Cuba	IIFT	6
Grapevines	Chile	UCHIL	14
Grapevines	Italy	UNIBO	84

- Table. List of the samples used in the microbiome study provided by Youri Uneau (ASSO, Guadeloupe), Wayne Myrie (CIB, Jamaica), Ndede Yankey (CSIR, Ghana), Carlos Oropeza (CICY, Mexico), Carlos Fredy Ortiz (COLPO, Mexico), Maritza Luis-Pantoja and Camilo Paredes-Tomás (IIFT, Cuba), Gert Pietersen (PTHSL, South Africa), Gerhard Pietersen (SU, South Africa), Nicola Fiore (UCHIL, Chile).

■ THE PRACTICE/INNOVATION PROPOSED BY TROPICSAFE

Setting up methods for microbiome characterization

For characterization of 'Ca. Phytoplasma' and 'Ca. Liberibacter' associated microbiomes, profiling by DNA sequencing could be an efficient approach. Development and implementation of next-generation sequencing technologies (NGS) have revolutionized methods in microbial ecology by enabling high-resolution community profiling. Methods and primers for the analysis of bacteria already exist and have been intensively used. When possible, use of target-specific primers, that amplify bacterial 16S rDNA sequences while avoiding amplification of plant organelle DNA sequences, is preferred. For these reasons, a set of primers (799F and 1193R) designed for the analysis of plant-associated bacterial communities (Hu *et al.*, 2018), was initially tested. However, phytoplasma DNA is not completely matching to this primer pair and therefore these primer sequences were optimized.

■ HOW IS TROPICSAFE IMPLEMENTING IT?

Amplification and sequencing procedures

Variants of the 799F and 1193R primers were optimized based on nucleotide alignments from 'Ca. Phytoplasma' and 'Ca. Liberibacter' ribosomal DNA sequences. These optimized primers contain degenerate nucleotides in order to accommodate their sequence variation compared to other bacteria. Nucleotides that are shown below in red are target specific, while the nucleotides in black are specific for the sequencing procedure. Degenerate nucleotides are underlined.

BacF1-799/1193 TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGAACMGGATTAGATACCCKG

BacR1-799/1193 GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGACGTNRTCCYCACCTTCC

These primers were tested using DNA from a number of 'Ca. Phytoplasma' and 'Ca. Liberibacter' infected host plants with an optimized PCR amplification protocol (94°C for 5 minutes followed by 25 cycles at 94°C for 30 seconds, 55°C for 30 seconds, 72°C for 1 minute, and a final elongation step at 72°C for 10 minutes). This resulted in clear DNA bands of the expected size. After optimization, samples primarily originating from Italy, Ghana, Cuba, South Africa, but also from other countries that had been collected by project partners, were characterized by Illumina sequencing and the sequencing reads were computationally and statistically analysed. In total, approximately 400 samples originating from grapevine, palm and citrus together with samples from alternate host plants and insect vectors were analysed.

- Example of amplification using the optimized 799/1193 degenerate primers on a set of DNA samples from different host plants (grapevine and palm). The band of interest is the strong band at approximately 500 nucleotides. At the left side of each panel, a molecular marker is shown.

■ HOW IS IT WORKING?

Bacterial differentiation results

The optimized method for characterization of microbial prokaryotic populations in plants infected with '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' and '*Ca. Liberibacter*' successfully amplified target prokaryotic DNA, while no notable amplification of plant organelle DNA was observed after taxonomic assignment of the sequence reads. This shows in the below figure that the proportion of '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' reads (pink bars) of the total microbiome in the individual samples is highly variable. Stacked vertical bars show the distribution of the microbial taxa within each sample in an example of a comparison between samples of palm, grapevine and a range of alternative hosts.

Generally, grapevine samples had a much higher proportion of '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' reads compared to other prokaryotes, and in several cases, phytoplasmas were taking up almost 100% of the sequence reads. Within phytoplasma reads, sequence variation was likewise observed. In the samples from palm, 71 different sequence variants were identified, and of these, 5 sequence variants were identified in several samples. In the samples from grapevine, 82 different sequence variants were detected, and 5 of these were identified in several samples and with notable read numbers in at least more than one sample. Therefore, these sequence variants are considered valid.

- Stacked vertical bars showing the relative abundance of *taxa*, present in each sample, at phylum level from grapevine, bindweed, oak, *Asteraceae*, maple and coconut. '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' reads are shown in pink. The Local Contribution to Beta Diversity (LCBD) is a comparative index of uniqueness with large values indicating the samples that have strongly different species compositions compared to the others. LCBD values are plotted as bubbles under stacked bar plots to indicate samples that differ markedly in their composition.

- Stacked vertical bars showing the relative abundance of the most abundant *taxa*, present in each sample. In the citrus samples (last four columns), HLB is within the *Alphaproteobacteria*, while phytoplasma are in the *Mollicutes*. The Local Contribution to Beta Diversity (LCBD) is a comparative index of uniqueness with large values indicating the samples that have strongly different species compositions compared to the other ones. LCBD values are plotted as bubbles under stacked bar plots to indicate samples that differ markedly in their composition.

KEY WORDS

Microbiome, amplification, bacteria, endophytes

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